

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Los Angeles
Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia

ENHANCING THE NURSE-PATIENT COMMUNICATION AND PATIENT
SATISFACTION

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Carolina Uranga

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Sadeeka Al-Majid, PhD, RN, FAAN, Team Leader
Laura Sarff, DNP, RN, MBA, CPHQ, NEA-BC, Team Member

May 2024

Author Note

Carolina Uranga - <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3216-7417>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13737769

© 2024 Carolina Uranga

ABSTRACT

Background: Interventions to enhance a trusting patient-nurse relationship are paramount to improving patient satisfaction. Communicating effectively and understanding the patient's perspective has lowered patients' anxiety and increased patients' sense of control and confidence regarding their health status. Purpose: Enhance The HOPE Experience Program by incorporating the Commit to Sit component and assessing its impact on patient satisfaction. The aims were to: a) increase nurses' knowledge and skills on the elements of the Commit to Sit; b) increase the number of nurses who implement Commit to Sit strategy; and c) evaluate patient satisfaction using the CAHPS Top Box Scores for nursing communication. Methods: Forty registered nurses in a 33-bed oncology unit received educational intervention between September and October 2023. A pre-post-test design was utilized to measure changes in knowledge, practice, and patient satisfaction using a survey, observations audits, and CAHPS Top Box Scores. Intellectus Statistics software was used to analyze pre-and post-data using paired and independent samples t-test with a significant level set at $P < .005$. Results: Over 50% of eligible nurses participated. The educational intervention significantly improved nurses' knowledge ($p < .001$) and skills ($p = .001$); but not patient satisfaction. Discussion: Implementation of Commit to Sit was possible. Barriers identified to sitting during patient interactions were insufficient chairs, possibly due to inconsistent patient room sizes. Conclusion: Ongoing education and observations of The HOPE Experience program and Commit to Sit strategies are vital to hardwiring them into practice.

Keywords: nurse-patient relationship, communication strategies, patient satisfaction, patient experience, nursing communication, AIDET, and commit to sit.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	viii
BACKGROUND	1
Problem Statement.....	2
Purpose Statement.....	6
Supporting Framework	6
Identifying the Triggering Issues or Opportunities.....	8
Purpose Statement.....	8
Decision Point One: Is the Topic a Priority	8
Team Formation.....	9
Assemble, Appraise, Synthesize the Body of Evidence and Decision Point Two	9
Design and Pilot Practice Change.....	10
Decision Point Three: Is Change Appropriate; Integration and Sustainability.....	10
Dissemination of Results	10
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	12
Overview.....	12
Communication.....	13
Nurse-patient Relationship/Interactions.....	15
Communication Strategies and Patient Satisfaction	16
Summary.....	19
METHODS	21
Design.....	21
Setting.....	21
Sample.....	21
Staff Education.....	22
Institutional Review Board Approval Process.....	22
Survey and Observation Timeframe	23
Measures	23
DNP Project	24
Data Collection	25

RESULTS	27
Demographic Characteristics	27
Knowledge Survey	28
The HOPE Experience Self-Assessment of Patient Interactions	28
The HOPE Experience Paired Observations	29
Commit to Sit Self-Assessment and Paired Observations	29
CAHPS Nursing Communication	30
DISCUSSION	31
Implications	33
Limitations	34
Recommendations	35
Conclusion	37
REFERENCES	39
APPENDIX A: The Iowa Model	49
APPENDIX B: Articles Searched from CINAHL	50
APPENDIX C: Articles Searched from PubMed	52
APPENDIX D: Articles Searched from Cochrane	53
APPENDIX E: Permission to Use the Iowa Model Decision Points	54
APPENDIX F: Institutional Review Board – Initial California State Fullerton	55
APPENDIX G: Institutional Review Board – Amendment California State Fullerton	58
APPENDIX H: Institutional Review Board – Initial City of Hope	61
APPENDIX I: Institutional Review Board – Approval City of Hope	63
APPENDIX J: Institutional Approval Letter to Use the Project Site	64
APPENDIX K: Permission to Use The HOPE Experience Educational Material	65
APPENDIX L: Knowledge Survey Questions	66
APPENDIX M: DNP Project Timeline	67
APPENDIX N: Nurse-Patient Interactions Self-Assessment	68

APPENDIX O: Consent to Participate	73
APPENDIX P: Observation Tool	77
APPENDIX Q: Results Demographic Characteristics	78
APPENDIX R: Results Knowledge Survey	80
APPENDIX S: Results The HOPE Experience Self-Assessment Composite Scores	81
APPENDIX T: Results The HOPE Experience Paired Observations Composite Scores	82
APPENDIX U: Results Commit to Sit Self-Assessment and Paired Observations	83
APPENDIX V: Results CAHPS Top Box Score Communication with Nursing	84

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This DNP journey has been challenging and fulfilling. I could not have done the academic portion without the support and dedication of wonderful professors that challenged me to do my best. I would like to express my heartfelt appreciation to Dr. Al-Majid for her exceptional guidance, mentorship, and support throughout this program. Dr. Al-Majid you have been a source of inspiration and knowledge, always pushing me to strive for excellence and for inspiring to be best version of myself. Thank you for all the time and effort that you have invested in me and for believing in me even when I didn't. Also, a big thank you to Dr. Sarff for your guidance, expertise, and support throughout my DNP program. A shout-out goes out to Cohort 11 for their fellowship and goodwill and especially, to Karla Hill. Karla, you are a kind and generous soul, and I am forever in your debt for your dedication to helping me succeed. To my office mates and my director, Annemarie Flood, your encouragement, and support was greatly appreciated. I can't forget the EHB nursing staff. I am so grateful for your participation in this project.

Lastly, I would like to thank my family, Emilio, Olivia, and especially my husband, Emilio. You have been my cheerleader, my rock, and my best friend. Your sacrifices and dedication have not gone unnoticed, and I am forever grateful for your unwavering support. I could not have done it without you. You have always told me "Go as far as your intellect will take you," okay, I think I am done now.

Background

Communication, verbal or non-verbal, is central to the nurse-patient professional relationship. Communication is how we can educate, inform, provide support, and compassionate care to patients and their families (Katz, 2019). During an encounter, an open and empathetic nurse can obtain personal knowledge and understanding of the patient's feelings and suffering (Holopainen et al., 2019; Takman & Stevenson, 1999). The quality of communication during health encounters is key to effective patient care (Cibanal et al., 2014, as cited in Granados-Gamez et al., 2021). Quality communication may include listening to, informing, and involving patients in their care (National Comprehensive Cancer Network, [NCCN®], 2023). From a patient-centered perspective, there are many ways to communicate, which include interpersonal, nurse-patient, and therapeutic communication (Granados-Gamez et al., 2021; Gutiérrez-Puertas et al., 2020). Many nursing theorists provide insight into the relationship between nurses and their patients and how communication can occur. The Rogers (1961) model speaks to the interaction and relationship between the patient (client) and the nurse (therapist) as having empathy, active listening, and feedback. Peplau's (1991) theory is founded on striving to understand the interpersonal relationships between the patient and the professional. Therapeutic communication is holistic and patient-centered, encouraging trust and creating a meaningful exchange between the patient and the nurse. Watson (1997) emphasized the importance of individualized attention, understanding, and listening (Granados-Gamez et al., 2021; Peplau, 1991; Rogers, 1961; Watson, 1997). These theories highlight aspects of communication that can promote a practical and engaging nurse-patient relationship. Improvement in nurse-patient communication can improve patient satisfaction, increase adherence to treatment plans, and decrease medical errors (Gillespie & Schiffman, 2018).

The nurse-patient relationship has been conceptualized as a caring or helping relationship based on the interactions between the nurse, patient, and/or family. It may be considered integral to providing care (Allande-Cussó et al., 2022). Good nurse-patient interactions can substantially decrease patient anxiety levels, increase the patient's sense of control and confidence, reduce hospital stays, and increase patient satisfaction with the care received (Allande-Cussó et al., 2022). Important behaviors and characteristics of the nurse that support the nurse-patient relationship include the nurses' ability to gain trust and rapport, show honesty and openness, being present when interacting with patients, communicating effectively when sharing information and listening to patients, and garnering understanding of the patient's perspective (Pratt et al., 2021).

Problem Statement

Regardless of the complexity of nursing care, patients expect compassionate and caring nurses who demonstrate effective communication skills and can apply the latest knowledge and clinical skills (Vega & Hayes, 2019). Nurses are involved in the direct care of patients 24 hours a day, and a patient's hospital experience relies on the nurses they encounter (Vega & Hayes, 2019). Nurses skilled in communication can improve the nurse-patient relationship and enhance patients' understanding of healthcare quality and treatment outcomes (Sethi & Rani, 2017). Effective nursing communication optimized through practice, experience, and reflection can improve the nurse's self-efficacy, confidence, and strengthen patient-centered care (Atashzadeh-Shoorideh et al., 2021). The consequences of ineffective communication can lead to bad outcomes, such as patient harm and even death (Blevins, 2023). Effective communication can be categorized into patient-nurse and healthcare system-related outcomes and can promote a comfortable and satisfactory patient experience (Afriyie, 2020).

The latest Gallup Poll in 2022 showed that only 48% of Americans rate healthcare quality as “excellent” or “good,” the lowest in 20 years. Fifty-two percent rate the quality of United States (US) healthcare as unsatisfactory (Saad, 2023). The patient’s experience of healthcare quality is monitored by the Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and System (HCAHPS) Survey. The federal government uses the HCAHPS survey to benchmark the patients’ perceptions of their hospital experience and publishes the results to the public. By making these results public, consumers can compare hospitals on standards of care that include pain management, responsiveness, communication, and noise (Sherwood & Barnsteiner, 2022). Hospitals are encouraged by the federal government to use the HCAHPS survey to monitor and report their performance data (Sherwood & Barnsteiner, 2022). The survey gathers the patients’ evaluation of their care experience and timeliness of care, which the Center for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) uses to objectively evaluate care between Medicare recipients (Naik, 2022). The HCAHPS survey is a 29-item survey tool used to collect data that measures the patient’s perception of care received during their hospitalization. The survey, also known as the CAHPS® Hospital Survey, is sent to a random sample of patients between 48 hours and six weeks after hospital discharge. The HCAHPS survey has 10 composite measures, six summarizing how well doctors and nurses communicate with patients, hospital staff responsiveness to the patient’s needs, staff communication about new medicines and discharge education, and how well patients understand their home care instructions. The other four composite measures survey the patient’s perceptions of cleanliness, the quietness of their rooms, the hospital’s overall rating, and whether they would recommend the hospital to family and friends (Center for Medicare and Medicaid Services, [CMS], 2021). The results of the HCAHPS are reported publicly as “Bottom”, “Middle,” and “Top” Box scores. The most positive response

is the “Top Box” response of “Always” for the four composite measures related to Communication with Doctors, Communication with Nurses, Communication About Medications, and Responsiveness of Hospital Staff. The “Middle Box” response is “Usually, and the “Bottom Box” response are “Sometimes” or “Never” (Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and System, [HCAHPS], 2024). Organizations can appraise the quality of health care provided by evaluating patient experience and patients’ perception of effectiveness and safety of care. Evaluation of a patient’s experience tells whether the encounter occurred as expected or how often it occurred (Always, Usually, Sometimes, and Never). For example, did the provider deliver clear communication in a healthcare setting if yes, how often did it occur (AHRQ, August 2022).

Patient experience is a multi-faceted and multidimensional concept. It is defined as the “sum of all interactions (personal, patient, and family), shaped by an organization’s culture that influences patient and family’s perceptions across the continuum of care” (Oben P., 2020; The Beryl Institute, 2023). Patient experience is an important measure for organizations to capture, as patients are actively selecting where they will receive care based on their evaluated experiences (Sherwood & Barnsteiner, 2022). Patient experience includes patient interactions with the healthcare system, healthcare plans, clinicians, hospital staff, clinics, and other healthcare facilities. Patient experience plays an important role in healthcare quality and includes many facets of healthcare delivery. Patients want to receive timely care, information that is easy to access, and expect excellent communication with healthcare providers (Agency for Healthcare Research & Quality [AHRQ], 2022). The patient’s experience may also provide insight into how well communication occurred with a provider or nurse (Gillespie & Schiffman, 2018; Sherwood & Barnsteiner, 2022). Some of the nursing specific HCAHPS survey questions are: “During your

hospital stay...How often did nurses treat you with courtesy and respect? How often did nurses listen carefully to you? How often did nurses explain things in a way you could understand?” (Sherwood & Barnsteiner, 2022, p. 165). The composite score of these questions provides a window to the patient’s perception of care received when “always” is selected or carried out (Lidgett, 2016). The HCAHPS survey offers the opportunity to compare nurse-sensitive measures nationally and regionally with other participating hospitals (Sherwood & Barnsteiner, 2022)

Patient satisfaction is a “measurement designed to obtain reports or ratings from patients about services received from an organization, hospital, physician, or health care provider” (Sherwood & Barnsteiner, 2022, p. 515). Patient satisfaction measures whether the patient’s expectations about their health encounter were met. Satisfaction ratings can differ from patient to patient based on the individual’s expectation of the care delivery (AHRQ, August 2022). The satisfaction score is based on many factors, including the patient’s overall care experience before, during, and after the care environment (Berkowitz, 2016). The terms patient satisfaction and patient experience are sometimes used interchangeably. For this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project, patient satisfaction was used when referring to patient outcomes as measured by the CAHPS survey at the Project Site. The CAHPS scores for nursing communication on a Medical Oncology Unit at a Comprehensive Cancer Center in Southern California are lower than the 90th percentile benchmark.

For the last two quarters of 2022-2023, the CAHPS Top Box Scores for the Nursing Domain: Overall Communication were as follows: Quarter One 2023: 74.4%, 26th percentile; and Quarter Four 2022: 72.3%, 19th percentile (Press Ganey, 2023). The Project Lead’s workplace provides tools and resources to improve the patient experience. In 2021, the

organization implemented The HOPE Experience: A Model of Human Compassion to improve the patient experience. This program is committed to exceptional and individualized care experiences for all patients, caregivers, and each other. It symbolizes values and actions to provide the best medical care and understanding that a patient's cancer journey is more than their diagnosis and treatment (City of Hope, 2023). Only the charge nurses and very few frontline staff from the Medical Oncology Unit have been trained to communicate and interact with patients and their families using this model. All new employees receive education on The HOPE Experience Program as part of their hospital orientation.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this DNP project was to implement an evidence-based nurse-patient communication strategy to improve the nurse-patient communication and enhance the patient satisfaction of adult oncology patients on the Medical Oncology Unit of a Cancer Center in Southern California. The aims of this project were achieved by a) increasing nurses' knowledge and skills on implementing the elements of the Commit to Sit strategy, b) documenting the number of nurses who implemented the new Commit to Sit strategy, and c) evaluating patient satisfaction as measured by the CAHPS Top Box Scores for nursing communication.

Supporting Framework

The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care is an evidence-based practice (EBP) process model that guides clinicians to conduct and implement EBP practice activities (Melnik et al., 2017; Tucker et al., 2021). The Iowa Model incorporates frameworks such as the Diffusion of Innovations, Roger's Theory, and the Quality Assurance Model for Using Research (Buckwalter et al., 2017; Titler et al., 2001). The Iowa Model was developed in 1994 and implemented at the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics to guide

nurses and other healthcare professionals in implementing the best evidence (Titler et al., 2001). The Iowa Model was updated in 2001 to include new terms and feedback loops, consider changes in the healthcare market, and use different types of evidence, such as case reports when research is unavailable (Titler et al., 2001). The Iowa Model has been used extensively in the United States and 130 countries, and there have been over 3,900 requests from educators, clinicians, researchers, and administrators to guide them in the EBP process. (Iowa Collaborative et al., 2017). The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care is the EBP model of choice for nurse leaders from Magnet-designated hospitals (Speroni et al., 2020).

The most recent Iowa Model was revised in 2015 to be more streamlined and easier to follow (Iowa Collaborative 2017). The Revised Iowa Model has seven steps and three decision points with feedback loops to guide the clinician through the EBP process. The first step of the model was simplified to five triggers to identify issues/opportunities and includes a reworded term “data/new evidence.” This new term considers risk management data, process improvement, internal and external benchmarking data, and financial data. The other four issues/opportunities are the clinical or patient-identified issue, accrediting agency requirements/regulations, organization, state, or national initiative, and philosophy of care. The revised model reflects initiatives recommended by national quality accrediting bodies such as the Joint Commission, national quality strategies such as the HCAHPS survey, and organizational, state, and international initiatives (Iowa Collaborative, 2017). The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Healthcare was used to guide this DNP project. The Iowa Model guided framing, organizing, and implementing the project using the seven steps and three decision points of the model (Appendix A).

Identifying the Triggering Issue or Opportunities

Step one of the Iowa Model is identifying triggering issues/opportunities. The medical oncology unit values patient satisfaction with its complex patients undergoing chemotherapy, investigational research-related treatments, or other aggressive treatments. Improving patient satisfaction scores to above the 90th percentile rank has been challenging for the director and manager of the unit. Integration of initiatives that align with the tenets of the organization is key to fostering high-quality care that is safe and improves outcomes (Pittsenbarger et al., 2019). Personalizing care for the patient and family is very important to the organization. The triggering issues for this DNP project are clinically related to patient problems, and philosophy of care, which are identified as lower than the benchmark for the CAHPS Top Box Scores Domain: Communication with Nurses at a Comprehensive Cancer Center.

Purpose Statement

Step two of the Iowa Model was to state the purpose or question of the DNP project. The purpose of this project is to improve nurse-patient communication and enhance patient satisfaction of adult oncology patients on a medical oncology unit. The CAHPS Top Box Score Domain will measure improvement in patient outcomes (patient experience OR patient satisfaction): Communication with Nurses with the goal of at or above the 90th percentile by Quarter One 2024. It will be guided by the population, intervention, comparison, and outcome (PICO) question: “In hospitalized oncology patients, does implementation of best practice nursing communication strategy, compared to usual care, improve patient outcomes?”

Decision Point One: Is the Topic a Priority

The next step is determining if the topic is a priority to the organization. The Project Lead met with the Senior Manager of the Office of Patient Experience to discuss supporting the

Project Lead's efforts to improve patient satisfaction. The Senior Manager expressed interest, support, and appreciated the opportunity to align the practice of The HOPE Experience with the Project Lead's efforts to improve nurse-patient communication and patient satisfaction. He provided resources such as The HOPE Experience educational material, patient satisfaction results, and connected the Project Lead with other staff within the department to assist as needed. The Project Lead also met with the unit manager and director to discuss the purpose statement and obtained their support to implement an EBP communication strategy on their unit. Therefore, implementing the HOPE Experience Program and the Commit to Sit Nurse-Patient Communication Strategy is a top priority for nursing leadership and the organization.

Team Formation

In step three, a team was formed with the unit's nursing manager, director, and the Unit-Based Council (UBC). During the UBC meetings, the Project Lead discussed nursing communication, patient satisfaction scores, and the importance of improving nurse communication satisfaction scores. Collaboration with the solid tumor nursing leadership, nursing staff, UBC, and the Patient Experience Department was important to implement a practice change.

Assemble, Appraise, and Synthesize the Body of Evidence and Decision Point Two

The next step in the algorithm involved assembling, appraising, and synthesizing the body of evidence. A review and synthesis of literature was performed to inform and evaluate the potential communication strategies available for the project using the PICO question in step two. Decision Point Two: Is there sufficient evidence? The review of the evidence found in the literature was appraised and synthesized by the Project Lead to inform the best practices for nurse-patient communication strategies to improve nurse-patient communication and patient

satisfaction. The themes that emerged from the synthesis of the literature are discussed in more detail in the “Review of the Literature” section.

Design and Pilot the Practice Change

In step five, the pilot design and practice change involved pre- and post-data collection, re-education of the nursing staff on The HOPE Experience Program and training on the Commit to Sit communication strategy and data analysis. Details of the design, sample, setting, ethical considerations, procedures, and evaluation of the practice change are available in the Methods section.

Decision Point Three: Is Change Appropriate; Integration and Sustainability

Decision Point Three is the next step in the model and asks if the change is appropriate to adopt into practice. The project site has a Patient Experience Department that monitors and tracks the HCAHPS patient satisfaction scores and values, improving the patient experience. In step six of the Iowa Model, integration and sustainment of the practice change is key to improving patient satisfaction. The DNP project integrated the Commit to Sit communication strategy into The HOPE Experience program. The sustainability of the communication strategy will be assessed by continued monitoring and evaluation of CAHPS Top Box Score Domain: Communication with Nurses, regular nursing observation of practice change. More details of the pilot design, implementation, and sustainability are available in the Methods and Discussion sections.

Dissemination of Results

Lastly, Step Seven of the Iowa Model is to disseminate the results. The Project Lead initially disseminated the results via poster presentation to faculty and colleagues at the Fourth Annual Health and Human Development research showcase, California State University-

Fullerton. Results will be shared with the organization's Patient Experience Department, sponsoring nurse leaders, and during Nursing Grand Rounds in July 2024. Future dissemination will occur by submitting an abstract for poster/podium at a regional, national, or international forum and a manuscript for consideration in a national journal (Iowa Collaborative, 2017).

Review of Literature

Overview/Search Strategies

The literature was reviewed using the Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), PubMed, and Cochrane Library databases. Search filters included dates from 2016 to 2023 and peer-reviewed articles published in English. The search terms used to identify relevant literature in CINAHL were as follows: “communication,” “empathy,” “emotional intelligence,” “nurse-patient relations,” “framework or model or theory or approach,” “communication skills training,” “communication methods,” “patient experience or patient satisfaction and communication and nursing,” “nurse-patient communication and patient satisfaction,” “commit to sit to improve nurse communication,” “commit to sit,” and “AIDET.” The CINAHL search yielded 498 articles (Appendix B). In PubMed, the search strategy used the Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms “nursing,” “empathy,” “communication,” and “framework” which yielded 34 articles (Appendix C). The Cochrane Library database search strategy terms included “nursing communication framework,” “nurse-patient relations,” “nursing and empathy,” “nursing communication skills” and “AIDET” which resulted in 47 articles (Appendix D). Research articles references were manually searched to capture articles not found in the electronic databases. A total of 579 articles were retrieved for title and subject relevance. Duplicates, editorials, content related to the pediatric population, midwifery, obstetrics, dementia, end-of-life care, and long-term care were excluded. What remained were 86 articles, which were further reviewed for relevance to the project topic. For the final literature review, 38 articles were deemed appropriate and were included in this review. Of the 38 articles used, 12 are qualitative studies (Afriyie, 2020; Allande-Cussó et al., 2022; Atashzadeh-Shoorideh et al., 2021; Bullington et al., 2019; Crawford et al., 2018; den Hertog & Niessen, 2021; Hermann et al.,

2019; Holopainen et al., 2019; Lam et al., 2020; Lundberg et al., 2020; Trotta et al., 2020; Rivai et al., 2020), seven quality improvement (Alamanioti & Lambrou, 2022; El-Shami, 2023; George et al., 2018; Irwin, 2020; Lidgett, 2016; Pittsenbargar et al., 2019; Skaggs et al., 2018), seven expert opinion (Barber, 2018; Blevins, 2023; Burgener, 2020; Gillespie & Shiffman, 2018; Joint Commission International, 2018; Katz, 2019; Vega & Hayes, 2019), two randomized controlled trials ([RCTs], Antonini et al., 2021; Düdener & Hallaç, 2023), two systematic reviews (Moore, et al., 2018; Granados-Gómez et al., 2021), two cohort (Amey et al., 2017; Li et al., 2022), three literature review (Borges et al., 2017; Crawford et al., 2017; Pratt et al., 2021), one quantitative (Register et al., 2020), one descriptive cross-sectional (Sethi & Rani, 2017), one mixed-methods (Krueger et al., 2021).

A search to identify relevant articles was performed to determine the state of the evidence and best practices related to communication strategies and patient satisfaction. The purpose of this DNP project was to implement an evidence-based nurse-patient communication strategy to enhance patient satisfaction of adult oncology patients in the Medical Oncology Unit of a Cancer Center in Southern California. This section will synthesize 38 articles from the current literature categorized into three themes to guide best practices for improving nursing communication and patient satisfaction. The themes are a) communication, b) nurse-patient relationship, and c) communication strategies and patient satisfaction. When used effectively as a communication strategy, communication can enhance the nurse-patient relationship/interaction and improve patient satisfaction.

Communication

Communication is defined by Merriam-(2023) online as “a process by which information is exchanged between individuals through a common system of symbols, signs or behavior”

(Merriam-Webster, 2023). In general, communication is a dynamic and cyclical process involving the exchange of information between people in multiple modes, such as written, verbal, non-verbal, or other mediums (Afriyie, 2020; Crawford et al., 2017). Communication is central to personal and professional relationships (Katz, 2019). Communication in nursing is complex due to multiple factors that can impact the meaningful exchange of facts, thoughts, feelings, and opinions shared between the patient and nurse (Afriyie, 2020). Factors such as mood, time, culture, language, gender, relationship, environment, and non-verbal gestures can impact how effectively communication is provided (Afriyie, 2020). Nurses must develop effective communication skills in many situations impacting care, such as teaching medication, conducting difficult conversations, conducting physical assessments, and planning discharge (Baille, 2017). Two key barriers to effective communication cited in the literature are culture and language, which can affect the nurse-patient relationship (Afriyie, 2020; Alamanioti & Lambrou, 2022; Borges et al., 2017; Crawford et al., 2017; Joint Commission International, 2018; Sethi & Rani, 2017). Misunderstanding of information and how it is perceived can lead to non-adherence to treatment, delay in discharge, and compromise patient safety (Joint Commission International, 2018). A key recommendation to minimize language barriers is using medical interpreters to assist with communication in all patient interactions throughout the continuum of care (Joint Commission International, 2018). Effective nursing communication is also part of the American Nurses Association (ANA) Nursing: *Scope and Standards of Practice* Standard 10. This standard points to pertinent actions and behaviors a competent professional should incorporate when communicating in all areas of practice (ANA, 2021). Nursing communication has been linked to higher patient satisfaction, improved patient health outcomes, and higher overall HCAHPS survey ratings (Amey et al., 2017). Effective communication can provide personalized care and

is foundational to the nurse-patient relationship or interactions (Atashzadeh-Shoorideh et al., 2021; Sethi & Rani, 2017).

Nurse-Patient Relationship/Interactions

Many aspects of the nurse-patient relationship impact how nursing care is provided to patients. The nurse-patient relationship is a nursing skill, an intervention, and fundamental to nursing care (Allende-Cusso et al., 2022). The nurse-patient relationship involves the nurse as the caregiver and the patient being cared for in the context of value and mutual respect focused on health promotion and the patient's well-being. Its effectiveness is determined by the quality of the caring therapeutic relationship (Taylor et al., 2023). Several studies include common humanistic factors such as active listening, communication, presence, empathy, trust, mutual respect, and cultural competence as essential components of the nurse-patient relationship (Allende-Cusso et al., 2022; Antonini et al., 2021; Borges et al. 017; Holopainen et al., 2019; Rivai et al., 2020). Empathy and caring behaviors such as therapeutic touch and being present can have a positive effect on nurse-patient interactions and perceptions of care (Allende-Cusso et al., 2022; Bullington et al., 2019; den Hertog & Niessen, 2021; Düdener & Hallaç, 2023; Rivai et al., 2020). Empathy is an objective understanding of another person's situation by identifying how they feel and communicating this understanding back to that person (Taylor et al., 2023). Empathy can be multidimensional, including cognitive (understanding), affective (compassion, sympathy, and concern), and behavioral (communication of other's feelings and perspective elements). The basis for a trusting nurse-patient relationship is established when the patient and family perceive that the nurse is empathetic and committed to helping them (Taylor et al., 2023). Specifically, when empathy is demonstrated, it has been associated with patient satisfaction and better patient outcomes (Crawford et al., 2018). Two RCTs implemented nurse training on caring

behaviors to improve the nurse-patient relationship/interactions and showed a positive effect on the caring behaviors of nurses (Antonini et al., 2021; Düdener & Hallaç, 2023). In both RCT's caring behaviors and interactions were measured using the Caring Nurse-Patient Interactions Scale based on Watson's Theory of Caring (Antonini et al., 2021; Düdener & Hallaç, 2023). Whereas other studies provided communication skills training to clinicians followed by interviews or observations to better understand their nurse-patient interactions and provide insight into their communication skills (Bullington et al., 2019; Crawford et al., 2018; den Hertog & Niessen, 2021). A scoping review of 21 articles identified three themes on the nurse-patient relationship. The themes were becoming acquainted with the patient as a person, relationship building is complex and takes time, nurse behaviors and characteristics that promote the relationship, and the patient's voice. This scoping review examined the importance of an effective nurse-relationship as being person-centered, showing comprehensive interpersonal and communication skills, and having a caring approach and empathetic understanding of the patient. These behaviors will benefit patients by making them feel at ease and cared for (Pratt et al., 2020). Overall, the studies on this topic focus on the nurse-patient relationship, which comprises of caring interactions and caring behaviors such as therapeutic touch and being present, empathy, and effective communication.

Communication Strategies and Patient Satisfaction

The various communication strategies uncovered in this literature review focused on nursing communication skills to improve patient satisfaction and or patient experience (El-Shami, 2023; George et al., 2018; Irwin et al., 2020; Krueger et al., 2021; Li et al., 2022; Lidgett, 2016; Pittsenbarger et al., 2019; Register, et al., 2019; Skaggs et al., 2018). Two qualitative studies that focused on nursing care provided insight into the patient's experience from the

patient's perspective. They highlighted the importance of nursing communication behaviors and interventions such as courtesy, respect, engagement, and effective teaching to improve patients' perception of their communication with nurses (Hermann et al., 2019; Trotta et al., 2020). The HCAHPS survey is one of the ways to collect data on patient satisfaction and experience. The survey does not ask patients to evaluate their satisfaction; instead, it asks them to report on parts of the experiences that are important to them (AHRQ, August 2022). The HCAHPS survey includes questions related to nursing performance and can be used to measure how effectively nurses communicate with patients (Gillespie & Schiffman, 2018; Sherwood & Barnsteiner, 2022). Several articles focused on improving HCAHPS scores using two communication strategies known as Commit to Sit (El-Shami, 2023; George et al., 2018; Lidgett, 2016; Pittsenbarger et al., 2019) and Acknowledge, Introduce, Duration, Explain, Thank You known as AIDET® (Barber, 2018; Burgener, 2020; Irwin, 2020; Li et al., 2022; Register et al., 2019; Skaggs et al., 2018). Commit to Sit is a communication strategy focused on sitting at eye level with the patient to promote a therapeutic relationship and enhance care. This strategy fosters active listening, trust, and patient engagement, which can improve nurse communication HCAHPS scores (George et al., 2018; Pittsenbarger et al., 2019). Post operative nurses trained to sit for three to five minutes improved patient satisfaction with nurse-patient communication. The overall satisfaction was 89.4%, nurses listened carefully was 92.2%, and nurses explained things was 90.2%. Nurse participation and satisfaction in the Commit to Sit initiative was measured via an audit tool, which showed 91% participation, with nurses reporting the initiative as helpful (El-Shami, 2023). The second strategy for enhancing nurse-patient communication is using the AIDET® communication framework. Each letter of the acronym AIDET® is a communication behavior practiced during interactions with patients/clients. The A stands for Acknowledge, the I

stands for Introduce, the D stands for Duration, the E stands for Explain, and the T stands for Thank You (Huron, 2023; Register et al., 2019). Several studies using this communication mode have resulted in an improvement of HCAHPS survey scores (Irwin et al., 2020; Li et al., 2022; Register et al., 2019; Skaggs et al., 2018). A systematic review of 17 RCTs assessed whether communication skills training for a mix of 1,240 healthcare providers (HCPs) was effective in changing the behavior of HCPs working with cancer patients, improving HCPs well-being, and their patient's health status and satisfaction (Moore et al., 2018). This systematic review included a meta-analysis of 10 RCTs, mainly from the outpatient setting, regarding HCPs communication skills. The systematic review found that HCPs in the intervention group were more likely to show empathy ($P = 0.0008$) and less likely to just provide facts without individualizing and offering support ($P = 0.05$), indicating an improvement in supportive skills (Moore et al., 2018). Empathy, as discussed earlier, is an important element of communication that can be incorporated into communication training. This systematic review included various patient outcome instruments to measure patient anxiety, quality of life, perception of the HCPs communication skills, or satisfaction with HCPs communication skills; however, none included the HCAHPS Survey to measure patient outcomes (Moore et al., 2018). Educating and incorporating evidenced-based communication strategies into practice may improve patient satisfaction.

This DNP project was focused on inpatient nursing care and used the CAHPS Survey Domain: Communication with Nursing to evaluate the changes in nurse-patient interactions and communication. Collectively, studies on the theme of communication strategies provided quality improvement efforts using Commit to Sit and AIDET® to enhance nursing communication skills and improve patient satisfaction.

Summary

Communication skills training is key to empowering nurses to communicate and interact effectively and improving patient satisfaction (Afriyie, 2020; Burgener, 2020). The influence of nursing care on the overall HCAHPS patient satisfaction scores is important since the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services' Value-Based Purchasing Program ties reimbursement to performance. Hospital revenues drive the monetization of caring with incentives to increase patient satisfaction scores largely impacted by nursing domain satisfaction scores (McClendon, 2017). This value-based purchasing incentive has prioritized patient satisfaction for hospitals and Communication with Nurses' domain is an important component of the overall rating (Trotta et al., 2020).

The Project Lead implemented Commit to Sit based on this extensive literature review on best practices to improve the nurse-patient relationship and enhance patient satisfaction. It reinforced a framework comparable to AIDET® called The HOPE Experience program. The HOPE Experience is based on four principles that guide the organization's patient experience and service recovery practices. These guiding principles help staff interact with patients, caregivers, and each other on a personal and human level. Each letter in the word HOPE represents a principle associated with the organization's values. H stands for connect with *heart* by acknowledging, making eye contact, and introducing yourself. O stands for *offer* service with collaboration and a sense of urgency by explaining your actions, asking if they have questions, and taking ownership of concerns until resolved. P stands for *personalize* by listening, validating, empathizing, clarifying, and respecting cultural uniqueness. Lastly, E stands for *end* with excellence by explaining the care and next steps, sharing contact information, and saying thank you (City of Hope, 2023). During the initial rollout in 2021, staff were educated on the HOPE

Experience program using patient-centered care scenarios. Each department and inpatient unit developed department-specific practices related to the HOPE Experience and principles (City of Hope, 2023). This allows each inpatient unit to tailor their department-specific practices to their patient population. East Hospital B (EHB) nurses can significantly contribute to the patient's experience by fully incorporating The HOPE Experience Program and Commit to Sit into their practice.

Methods

The focus of this DNP project was to integrate the Commit to Sit communication strategy into The HOPE Experience Program and enhance nurse-patient communication and patient satisfaction of adult oncology patients in a Medical Oncology Unit. This DNP project modified The HOPE Experience educational material to include the Commit to Sit component and educated and trained nursing staff on communication strategies. This section will review the design, setting, sample, participants, ethical considerations, and procedures to implement the practice change.

Design

An evidence-based approach was used to achieve the project's objectives. Changes in knowledge acquisition following targeted education on The HOPE Experience Program and Commit to Sit communication strategies were measured using a pre-and post-test design. This DNP project used The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Healthcare to guide this practice change.

Setting

This project was implemented in the adult medical oncology unit. This unit is located at a Magnet designated, National Cancer Institute and Comprehensive Cancer Center in Southern California. The medical oncology unit is comprised of 33 beds including six double occupancy rooms. Forty percent of patients in this unit are adults 65 years and older.

Sample/Participants

The participants included in this sample were all the registered nurses assigned to work the medical oncology unit between September 2023 and December 2023. Float nurses and nurse assistants were excluded from participation in the project. All eligible nurses were verbally

informed that their participation was voluntary. The nurses were also assured of confidentiality, minimal risk to participate, and their right to withdraw at any time without consequence. Informed consent was provided and obtained from participants by completing the baseline anonymous survey. For the pre-and post-observation audits, the Project Lead asked the participant for permission to be observed and the nurse was observed after verbal consent was given. Confidentiality of the participants observed was ensured by using initials on the observation audit forms that only the Project Lead could access. Compensation was not provided for participation in the project.

Staff Education

Prior to the educational intervention, the Project Lead observed and documented the baseline nurse-patient interactions of EHB nurses using The HOPE Experience core practices and the Commit to Sit communication strategy during their shifts. Multiple educational in-person sessions were available to nurses during their weekend shifts, usually one to two nurses at a time. The presentation slides were displayed on a laptop and the educational session lasted 10-15 minutes. The education included The HOPE Experience core principles, corresponding care practices, and the Commit to Sit Communication Strategy.

Institutional Review Board Approval Process

Approval to use the Iowa Model for this DNP project was obtained by the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics (Appendix E). Institutional review board (IRB) approval from California State University-Fullerton (CSUF) and City of Hope National Medical Center was secured before the project commenced at the site. (Appendices F, G, H, I) A letter of support to implement the project was granted from the Nurse Executive Director of the Medical Oncology Unit (Appendix J). Permission to use The HOPE Experience: A Model of Human Compassion's

educational material was obtained from the Senior Program Manager, Office of the Patient Experience (Appendix K). Survey and observation data was stored and maintained safely for this project by the Project Lead on a password-protected laptop.

Survey and Observation Timeframe

The Project Lead started collection of baseline observation data from Saturday, September 1 to Monday, September 11, 2023. The anonymous baseline nursing demographic, self-assessment, and knowledge surveys were collected from Wednesday, September 13 to Tuesday, October 3, 2023. The in-person educational intervention with an immediate post-knowledge survey was provided from Friday, September 22, 2023, to Monday, October 9, 2023. The post-observation audits were conducted between Sunday, October 22, 2023, and Saturday, November 11, 2023. Approximately one month after the educational intervention, the nurses completed an anonymous post self-assessment and knowledge survey from Tuesday, October 24, 2023, to Tuesday, November 28, 2024.

Measures

Practice change and knowledge acquisition were assessed subjectively using pre- and post-self-assessment surveys; and objectively using pre-and post-knowledge surveys and pre-and post-observation audits (objective) to determine the effectiveness of change. The patient outcome measure used to evaluate pre- and post-patient satisfaction was the CAHPS Survey scores for the nursing communication domain. It is important to note that patients prefer nurses and providers to sit instead of stand during patient encounters (El-Shami, 2023; Pittsenbarger et al., 2019).

Process and outcome measures were evaluated to determine changes in practice and patient satisfaction scores. The first process measure was assessed using the pre- and post-knowledge level survey (objective) results with mean scores. It included the number of nurses

that participated in the educational intervention. The knowledge survey was collected at baseline, immediately after, and approximately one month after the educational intervention. The knowledge survey included five questions about The HOPE Experience, Commit to Sit, nurse-patient relationship, and effective communication (Appendix L). The second process measure was evaluated by conducting pre- and post-weekly random observations (objective) of nurses during their shifts to assess how many nurses used the Commit to Sit and The HOPE Experience Program communication strategies. The observation audit checklist included components of The HOPE Experience Program's four principles and their corresponding core practices, along with the Commit to Sit communication strategy to assess the performance of practice change. The third measure was an outcome measure and was patient related. It appraised changes in patient satisfaction by tracking and monitoring the CAHPS Top Box Scores pre-project implementation and three months post-project implementation.

DNP Project Timeline

The project timeline (Appendix M) started in March 2023 with a review of the literature identification of EBP communication strategies and was completed by April 2023. From May to June 2023, the project site was identified and a letter of approval from the project site was received from the Project Site Sponsor. The Project Lead presented the project for defense to the Team Lead and Team Member and project approval was granted. From July to September 2023, the Project Lead submitted the IRB application for review to both the project site and CSUF with approval obtained in August 2023. Data collection started in early September 2023 with observation audits. From October to December 2023, pre- and post-data collection was completed. The pre-and post-data results were analyzed beginning in January 2024 and finalized in March 2024. The Project Lead submitted an abstract to the CSUF Health and Human

Development Department, which was accepted for poster presentation in March 2024. In April 2024, the Project Lead presented the poster at the 4th Annual CSUF Health and Human Department showcase and presented the DNP project for final dissemination and defense to the Team Lead, Team Member, faculty, and colleagues at Dissemination Day.

Data Collection

Implementation of the project involved education and training of EHB nursing staff on The HOPE Experience program and the Commit to Sit Communication Strategy. Before the targeted education was disseminated, a baseline knowledge and nursing demographics survey was collected from EHB nursing staff (Appendix N). The participants' consent to participate in the study was obtained by reading the project's full description before completing the baseline survey. (Appendix O) Nursing demographic information was collected at baseline, including gender, education, shift worked, years of experience, years of experience at this facility, race, ethnicity, The HOPE Experience training received, and if they sat during patient encounters. The baseline survey was accessible via a QR code or on paper near the charge nurse's desk in case the survey was not completed before the education was presented. Most nurses preferred to complete the surveys using the QR code. Additionally, nurses were observed (objective data) during their patient interactions to check what The HOPE Experience Program and Commit to Sit communication strategies were being practiced.

For the pre-and post-test design, an anonymous survey was created in Microsoft Forms to collect baseline demographic data, pre- and post-self-assessment of nurse-patient interactions, and pre-and post-knowledge information. The self-assessment survey of nurse-patient interactions included principles, core practices from The HOPE Experience Program framework and sitting practices during patient encounters. The audit tool was also developed using

Microsoft Forms to collect pre- and post-observations of nurse-patient interactions. The observation tool (Appendix P) included the frequency of nurse-patient interactions such as making eye contact, acknowledging the patient, introducing themselves, explaining procedures and plan of care, asking if they have any questions, asking if they can do anything else, saying thank you, and sitting during the encounter.

The education was presented in person using PowerPoint slides over three to four weekends to maximize the dissemination of content to the weekend teams and during the week as needed. A unit roster was used to track staff the number of staff trained. Ongoing evaluation of the project included a review of the education slides to improve the overall staff education; however, no updates to the education slides were necessary. Immediately after the presentation, a post-knowledge survey was accessible via a QR code for participants to complete online. One month after the education, the staff were asked to complete the same online self-assessment of nurse-patient interactions and a knowledge survey to determine changes from the baseline.

Results

This section will review the project's results to enhance nurse-patient communication and patient satisfaction. Intellectus Statistics™ software was used to sort and analyze data points from the baseline nursing survey, pre- and post-knowledge survey, self-assessment of nurse-patient interactions, and pre-and post-observations of nurse-patient interactions. Descriptive statistics were used for nursing demographic data, the number of random audits, and the number of nurses educated during the implementation phase. The pre-and post-self-assessment of nurse-patient interactions was obtained via an anonymous survey; therefore, a two-tailed independent *t*-test was conducted to examine whether any changes in nurse-patient interactions were statistically significant in pre- and post-educational intervention. The observations audits were not collected anonymously, and a paired samples *t*-test was conducted to determine if there were any statistically significant changes in observed nurse-patient interactions, including Commit to Sit behaviors. Statistical significance was based on the *p-value* of $<.05$ for all tests. The knowledge survey was collected at three time points and an analysis of the variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine any significant difference in the time points. Results of the pre-and-post CAHPS Survey for nursing communication were evaluated to determine if there was a change in patient satisfaction scores after implementing the communication strategies.

Demographic Characteristics

More than half of the 45 eligible nurses participated in the DNP project. The most common characteristics observed before the intervention were as follows: the majority worked day shifts (n=22, 62.86%), had 2-5 years of experience at City of Hope (n=17, 48.57%), had 6-10 years of nursing experience (n=17, 48.57%), held a BSN as their highest nursing education degree (n=31, 88.57%), identified as female (n=29, 82.86%), identified as non-Hispanic/Non-

Latino (n=27, 77.3%), identified as Asian in race (n=25, 71.43%), and had undergone The HOPE Experience Training (n=16, 45.71%). Details regarding frequencies and percentages can be found in Appendix Q.

Knowledge Survey

Forty nurses completed the educational intervention and post-knowledge survey. The pre- and post-knowledge survey results were collected at three different time points and analyzed using ANOVA statistics based on a *p-value* of $<.05$ (Appendix R). To analyze the differences among the variables based on a *p-value* of $<.05$. A *t*-test was used to calculate between each group combination. The mean of points for Timepoint 1 ($M= 3.51$) was significantly smaller than Timepoint 2 ($M=4.47$), with a $p<.001$. The mean of Timepoint 2 ($M=4.47$) was considerably larger than for Timepoint 3 ($M=3.76$) $p = .003$. The analysis showed a statistically significant knowledge acquisition ($p<.001$).

The HOPE Experience Self-Assessment of Patient Interactions

The self-assessment survey of The HOPE Experience Program core principles and corresponding practice behaviors were tabulated and converted to a composite score. A two-tailed independent samples *t*-test of the self-assessment pre- and post-composite scores was conducted to assess whether the mean differences of each category were different than zero. The pre-H and post-H, pre-O and post-O, pre-P and post-P, pre-E and post-E results were not significant ($t(52) = -0.78, p=0.440$; $t(52) = -0.81, p = 0.424$; $t(52) = -1.06, p=0.296$; $t(52) = -0.23, p=0.821$, respectively). The self-assessment for all the composite scores pre-HOPE and post-HOPE was analyzed to determine the effectiveness of the practice change in pre- and post-education interventions. The two-tailed independent samples *t*-test with a *p-value* of $.05$ was not statistically significant ($t(52) = -0.71, p=.479$). The findings indicate that the mean of all

composite scores did not differ significantly between the pre-and post-categories. A total of 35 nurses completed the baseline nursing demographics, knowledge survey, self-assessment of their practice behaviors for each of The Hope Experience Program's core principles and Commit to Sit strategy. Nineteen nurses completed the post self-assessment survey (Appendix S).

The HOPE Experience Paired Observations

A two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was conducted for each of the observed composite scores to examine whether the mean differences of each category were different than zero. For pre-and post-data, each domain of HOPE was analyzed individually. The individual results for the pre-and post H as well as the pre-and post P were not significant ($t(31) = -0.30, p=.768$; $t(31) = -1.23, p=.229$). However, the individual pre-and post-O and pre-and post-E results were significant with ($t(31) = -2.78, p=.009$; $t(31) = -2.44, p=.021$).

Additionally, a two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was performed to analyze whether the difference in means of all pre- and post-composite scores was significantly different from zero. The mean for this analysis is the composite of all domains of HOPE. The mean of all the pre-composite scores ($M= 28.75$) was significantly lower than the post-composite scores ($M= 29.78$). The overall findings of the pre-HOPE and post-HOPE two-tailed paired samples *t*-test for all composite scores were statistically significant ($t(31) = -3.61; p=.001$). (Appendix T).

Commit to Sit Self-Assessment and Observations

A two-tailed independent samples *t*-test showed a significant difference between pre- and post-self-assessment for Sitting During the Encounter ($t(52) = -3.42, p = .001$). Thirty-five nurses surveyed at baseline provided their self-assessment of nurse-patient interactions, which included whether they never sat 25.7% ($n=9$), sometimes sat 48.6% ($n=17$), usually sat 25.7% ($n=9$), or always sat (0%) during patient encounters. Of the 19 participants who completed the post-self-

assessment survey, zero indicated they never sat, 47.4% (n=9) sometimes sat, 26.3% (n=5) usually sat, and 21.1% (n=4) always sat during patient encounters (Appendix U).

The result of a two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was conducted to determine whether the mean difference of the pre-and post-observation analysis for Sitting During the Encounter was substantially different than zero. The results indicated the two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was statistically significant ($t(31) = -3.75, p < .001$). Thirty-two unique nurses participated in the pre-and post-observation audits of The HOPE Experience Program and the Commit to Sit communication strategies.

CAHPS Nursing Communication

This intervention did not impact the CAHPS Nursing Communication satisfaction scores. Nurses treat you with respect, Nurses listen carefully, and Nurses explain the way you understand, were the three questions evaluated for top box satisfaction scores. The top box score only includes questions answered as “always.” Improvement was seen in the 4th Quarter 2023 in mean scores and percentile rankings during the intervention and observations for two out of three questions. The mean scores improved from 74 to 86 for the question, “Did the nurses treat you with respect?” The improved scores increased the CAHPS rankings from the 27th to the 53rd percentile. Similarly, the mean scores improved significantly from 71 to 82 for assessing whether “Nurses explain the way you understand.” The increase in mean scores also increased CAHPS rankings from the 27th to the 87th percentile. For the “Nurses listen to you carefully,” there was a decrease in mean scores and rankings. In the first quarter of 2024, all mean scores and rankings decreased for all three questions (Appendix V).

Discussion

This DNP project suggests that enhancing nurse-patient communication may impact patient satisfaction. Implementing a Commit to Sit communication strategy was feasible. Yet, this project's findings are inconsistent with other studies that have shown improved patient satisfaction after implementing a Commit to Sit strategy (George et al., 2018; Pittsenbargar et al., 2019). In the radiology department, the patient satisfaction scores fluctuated between 38% and 100% during the evaluation period of two years. Finally, they increased from 75% to 100% over the last three months of the study period (Pittsenbargar et al., 2019). A 30-bed medical surgical unit saw a steady increase in patient satisfaction, scoring 87 a year after implementing the Commit to Sit program (George et al., 2018). Considering that the post-implementation period for this project was only three months, a more extended evaluation period may be necessary to assess patient outcomes and determine if patient satisfaction can be improved.

Addressing patient dissatisfaction in healthcare is essential to maintaining quality and involves focusing on caring in practice. The patient and nurse can engage in a caring relationship, which can become a loving moment. However, an authentic presence is needed to develop and sustain these moments (Pajinkihar et al., 2017). The Commit to Sit Communication Strategy focuses on sitting at eye level with the patient to promote a therapeutic and trusting relationship by actively listening and engaging with the patient (George et al., 2018; Pittsenbarger et al., 2019). Most hospital complaints from patients derive from healthcare providers' attitudes and lack of communication skills. Patient-centered communication skills, which include building therapeutic relationships, empathy, and compassionate behaviors, can be challenging for nurses during their shifts. Training in communication skills is needed since

nurses typically spend more time in direct patient interactions than other providers and can shape the patient's perception of care and satisfaction (El-Shami, 2023; Skaggs et al., 2017).

Organizations want to improve patient satisfaction to drive service reimbursement, patient recommendations and referrals, and enhance brand recognition (Irwin, 2020). This DNP Project also reinforced the HOPE Experience Program, very similar to the communication framework AIDET®. The HOPE Experience Program framework provides a person-centered approach to caring for patients, their caregivers, and each other by connecting with heart, offering collaboration and service with a sense of urgency, personalizing, and ending with excellence. Commit to Sit is a communication strategy that has been shown to improve the nurse-patient communication. The HOPE Experience Program was implemented at the Project Site in 2021 to improve patient satisfaction. It is important to collaborate with partners on programs that will enhance engagement, shared decision-making, and empathetic and compassionate care (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, [IHI], 2023). This DNP project aligns with the organization's strategic initiatives to improve the patient experience.

This DNP project aimed to a) increase nurses' knowledge and skills on implementing the elements of the Commit to Sit strategy, b) document the number of nurses who implemented the new Commit to Sit strategy, and c) evaluate patient satisfaction as measured by the CAHPS Top Box Scores for nursing communication. The results of this DNP project indicate that aspects of The HOPE Experience principles and behaviors were reinforced and the Commit to Sit as a communication strategy was possible to implement. Both are important strategies to hardwire into practice to develop trusting and caring relationships with patients and families. Although patient satisfaction CAHPS Top Box nursing communication mean scores improved by 10 points

for two of the three nursing communication questions, they were not sustained during the post-evaluation period.

Implications

Patient satisfaction depends on the quality of the nurse-patient relationship. Focusing on professional communication using appropriate skills may improve the patient's satisfaction with the nursing care received. The quality of communication by nurses is important to patients and dissatisfaction with nursing care may be attributed to nurses not considering their preferences and opinions regarding their plan of care, not confirming their understanding of important treatments, more concerned with the nursing task than listening to their concerns, and not treating the patient like an individual (Lofti et al., 2019). A qualitative descriptive study design of recently discharged patients (n=49) aimed to understand the patient's communication experience with nurses. The study findings indicated that the participants' perception of nursing communication alone was not the only factor that drove patient satisfaction. Other factors, such as the nurses' attentiveness, proactive response to patient concerns, and effective teaching contributed to improved satisfaction with nursing communication. The study also found a misalignment between the participants' experiences and the HCAHPS nursing communication questions: "Nurses listen to you carefully," "Nurses treat you with respect," and Nurses explain the way you understand." The participants expressed that certain behaviors (courtesy and respect) were intrinsic in active listening, and courtesy and respect and attentive listening were inherent in being educated clearly (Trotta et al., 2020). The participants perceived engagement by nurses as making eye contact, smiling, not being sidetracked, or rushed, listening, asking thoughtful questions, and providing reassurance during nurse-patient interactions (Trotta et al., 2020).

Prominent organizations, such as the Institute of Medicine (IOM) and the NCCN®, support patient-centered care to deliver high-quality care in healthcare systems (NCCN®, 2023). The project site is part of the NCCN®, which values and supports caring for patients and their families meaningfully by listening to, informing, and engaging patients in their care (NCCN®, 2023). The essence of caring is important and is felt when we connect by listening and looking to comprehend the other person's experience (Burkhartzmeyer et al., 2021). The essence of nursing is authentic caring with the responsibility of focusing on the patient's profound caring needs. Authentic caring can be mutual for both the patient and nurse, with nurses affecting the patient's life and the nurse replenishing their commitment to their vocation. Patients expect and want more profound levels of connection with their nurses. When patients connect with nurses, it can leave a long-lasting feeling of well-being and healing (McClendon, 2017). It's important to recognize the essential role nurses play in driving patient satisfaction and the patient's perceived experience of care received.

Limitations

There were limitations during the project implementation. Firstly, some of the observed limitations included decreased opportunities to sit while interacting with the patients and their families or caregivers due to the lack of chairs in the patient rooms. Limited chairs may have been related to smaller room sizes and double occupancy rooms. Secondly, other limitations were the pre- and post-self-assessment nursing survey participants were not matched, and the results may have been affected by different nurses answering the questions; however, they were still nurses from the same unit. The latter and the small sample size of the post-self-assessment survey limited the ability to generalize the results to other units. Thirdly, there is the possibility that nurses may prefer to stand instead of sitting due to not understanding the benefits of the

communication strategy (George et al., 2018). Ongoing education should be provided to practicing nurses on the importance of sitting with patients, providing comfort and support, making eye contact, and holding the patient's hands, which encourages the practice of human caring (Pajinikhar et al., 2019). Finally, more time may be needed to evaluate CAHPS scores for nursing communication. Due to the project's time constraints, only three months post-implementation were reviewed and possibly one year may provide a better assessment of the project's patient outcome measures as related to the CAHPS patient satisfaction scores (George et al., 2018; Lidgett, 2016; & Pittsenbarger et al., 2019).

Recommendations

At the unit level, the Commit to Sit Communication Strategy, self-assessment survey observation audits, and knowledge survey showed statistically significant results; however, recommendations to improve compliance and sustain this DNP project are warranted. Education alone does not hardwire a change in practice (Skaggs et al., 2018). Therefore, this Project Lead recommends ongoing staff education on the Commit to Sit and The HOPE Experience Program to reinforce the communication strategy. The Project Lead recommends random observation audits to determine whether the nursing staff practices the strategies with optimal quality and frequency. To improve compliance with sitting during patient interactions due to the lack of chairs, a possible consideration would be to provide folding chairs in rooms that lack adequate sitting capacity and limited space. Folding chairs have a smaller profile than the bulky chairs currently placed in patient rooms. Staff, caregivers, and visitors can use the folding chairs as needed. When sitting is possible, it is recommended that the patient be asked for permission to sit, which allows the patient to control the situation (Lidgett, 2016).

At the organizational level, The Patient Experience Department supports The HOPE Experience Program, which aims to provide consistency in how staff interact with patients and their families and create a healing and caring environment. Currently, new employees are educated on The HOPE Experience strategies by the Patient Experience Department staff during new-hire hospital orientation. The Project Lead recommends adding the Commit to Sit strategy to The HOPE Experience session during new hire orientation and promoting this EBP communication strategy from the start. The HOPE Experience department at the project site also conducts monthly Patient Experience Rounds. The Patient Experience Rounds include leadership from various departments such as Medicine, Executive Suite, Nursing, Physical Therapy, Pharmacy, Nutrition Services, Patient Advocacy, Pharmacy, and Facilities. Taking a few minutes to connect with patients cultivates relationships and demonstrates caring and compassion (Lidgett, 2016). These rounds may allow leadership to Commit to Sit when talking to hospitalized and ambulatory patients and their caregivers to understand better their journey, perceptions of care, and the quality of their experience. These rounding sessions allow for just-in-time customer service recovery, identification of systemic issues, and other issues not normally captured in surveys such as the Press Ganey Survey. The Patient Experience Rounds are followed by a discussion forum to collectively address the issues and find solutions (V. Trisal, personal communication, April 3, 2024). The Patient Experience Rounds may be another opportunity for the Commit to Sit communication strategy to be implemented at the highest leadership level and incorporate this EBP communication strategy from the top down.

The final recommendation by this Project Lead is to enhance the focus on the genuine connection between the nurses and patients by asking patients about their perceptions of the encounter. Nurses' Caring behaviors can be evaluated using Watson's Theory of Human Caring,

which is widely used in clinical practice, research, and education (Gunawan et al., 2022). As nursing care becomes more and more complex, Watson's Theory has the potential to provide the basis for contemporary nursing practice. The Watson Caritas Patient Score is a validated instrument used in clinical research to assess the caring practices of healthcare clinicians from the viewpoint of the patient (Pajinikhar et al., 2019). Watson's Caring Science & Human Caring Theory offers other validated tools that measure caring practices for the Preceptor, Co-worker, Self, Leader, and Organization (Watson's Caring Science Institute, 2024). Using Watson's Theory and tools to assess caring behaviors and how they can impact nurse and patient connectedness is an important consideration for future research.

Conclusion

The purpose of this EBP project was to enhance The HOPE Experience Program by incorporating the Commit to Sit communication strategy as part of the nurses' interaction with patients during their shift and evaluate its effect on patient satisfaction. The statistically significant practice change results of the nurse observations (objective) and self-reported nursing survey (subjective) showed that nurses could include the Commit to Sit Communication Strategy during their shifts. The impact on patient satisfaction as measured by the CAHPS scores for nursing communication was not evident and the unit did not reach the 90th percentile goal one quarter post implementation of the DNP Project. More time to evaluate the project, reinforcement of communication strategies, and follow-up may be needed to fully appreciate any changes in mean scores and percentile ranking in the CAHPS Nursing Communication scores post-implementation. The Commit to Sit communication strategy may allow staff from all organizational levels to engage and connect with patients more meaningfully and enhance communication, improving patient satisfaction and experience.

The Project Lead recently participated in Patient Experience Rounds on EHB, and a patient expressed dissatisfaction with some of the care he had received in the past. The patient also recounted an experience in which one of the night shift nurses sat with him and listened to his concerns, and he said he was tearful during the interaction because he felt heard. Nurses can impact the patient's experience by sitting for a few minutes and connecting authentically, one patient at a time. By incorporating Commit to Sit with The HOPE Experience into day-to-day practice, healthcare clinicians can create a more person-centered care setting, enhance communication, and improve patient satisfaction and outcomes.

References

- American Nurses Association. (2021) *Nursing: scope and standards of practice*. (4th ed.).
American Nurses Association
- Agency for Healthcare Research & Quality. (2022, August 1). What is patient experience?
<https://www.ahrq.gov/cahps/about-cahps/patient-experience/index.html>
- Afriyie, D. (2020). Effective communication between nurses and patients: An evolutionary concept analysis. *British Journal of Community Nursing*, 25(9), 438-445.
<https://doi.org/10.12968/bjcn.2020.25.9.438>
- Alamanioti, K., & Lambrou, G. I. (2022). Communication of patients and healthcare personnel during the diagnostic radiological process. *Journal of Research and Practice on the Musculoskeletal System*. 6(20), 55-64. <https://doi.org/10.22540/JRPMS-06-055>
- Allande-Cussó, R., Fernández-García, E., & Porcel-Gálvez, A. M. (2022). Defining and characterising the nurse-patient relationship: A concept analysis. *Nursing Ethics*, 29(2), 462–484. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09697330211046651>
- American Psychological Association. (2020). *Publication manual of the American psychological association*. (7th ed.). Author.
- Amey, A. L., Burlingame, E. E., Welch, K., Moakler, M., & Fahey, L. (2017). Nurse communication's effect on CMS Star Ratings. *Nursing Management*, 48(8), 9-14.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.NUMA.0000521580.09882.3f>
- Antonini, M., Bellier-Teichmann, T., O'reilly, L., Cara, C., Brousseau, S., Weidmann, J., Roulet-Schwab, D., Ledoux, I., Konishi, M., Pasquier, J., & Delmas, P. (2021). Effects of an educational intervention to strengthen humanistic practice on haemodialysis nurses' caring

- attitudes and behaviours and quality of working life: a cluster randomised controlled trial. *BMC Nursing*, 20(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-021-00729-6>
- Atashzadeh-Shoorideh, F., Mohtashami, J., Farhadzadeh, M., Sanaie, N., Zadeh, E. F., Beykmirza, R., & Abdoljabari, M. (2021). Humanitarian care: Facilitator of communication between the patients with cancer and nurses. *Nursing Practice Today*, 8(1), 70-78. <https://doi.org/10.18502/npt.v8i1.4493>
- Baillie, L. (2017). An exploration of the 6Cs as a set of values for nursing practice. *British Journal of Nursing*, 26(10), 558-563. <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjon.2017.26.10.558>
- Barber, S. (2018). Patient care in decline: AIDET as a tool for improvement. *Radiologic Technology*, 89(4), 419-421.
- Berkowitz, B. (January 31, 2016). The patient experience and patient satisfaction: Measurement of a complex dynamic. *Online Journal of Issues in Nursing*. 21(1), Manuscript 1. <https://doi.org/10.3912/OJIN.Vol21No01Man01>
- The Beryl Institute (2020). *Defining patient experience*. Retrieved May 1, 2023. <https://www.theberylinstitute.org/page/DefiningPX>
- Blevins, S. (2023). Strategies for effective patient communication. *Medsurg Nursing*, 32(2), 125-126.
- Bonnel, W., & Smith, K. V. (2021). *Proposal writing for clinical nursing and DNP projects*. Springer Publishing Company.
- Borges, J. W., Magalhães Moreira, T. M., Braz da Silva, D., Oliveira Loureiro, A. M., & Bezerra de Meneses, A. V. (2017). Adult nursing-patient relationship: Integrative Review oriented by the king interpersonal system. *Journal of Nursing UFPE/Revista de*

Enfermagem UFPE, 11(4):1769-78. <https://doi.org/10.5205/reuol.9763-85423-1-SM-1104201727>

Bullington, J., Söderlund, M., Sparén, E. B., Kneck, Å., Omérov, P., & Cronqvist, A. (2019). Communication skills in nursing: A phenomenologically-based communication training approach. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 39, 136-141.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2019.08.011>

Burgener, A. M. (2020). Enhancing communication to improve patient safety and to increase patient satisfaction. *Health Care Manager*, 39(3), 128-132.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/HCM.0000000000000298>

Burkhartmeyer, H. L., Preston, H. R., Arcand, L. L., Mullenbach, D. L., Nelson, D. E., Lorentz, P. A., & Stevens, S. K. (2021). Speaking to the heart of our patients: An empathic communication education initiative. *The Journal of Continuing Education in Nursing*, 52(7), 319-325. <https://doi.org/10.3928/00220124-20210611-06>

Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services (2021, December 1). *HCAHPS: Patients' perspectives of care survey*. <https://www.cms.gov/Medicare/Quality-Initiatives-Patient-Assessment-Instruments/HospitalQualityInits/HospitalHCAHPS>

Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services. (2021, March 1). *HCAHPS fact sheet*. <https://www.hcahpsonline.org>

City of Hope (2023). *The hope experience. A model of human compassion*. iHope Your City of Hope Community Intranet. <https://www.cityofhope.org/>

Merriam-Webster. (2023). Communication. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/communication>

- Crawford, T., Candlin, S., & Roger, P. (2017). New perspectives on understanding cultural diversity in nurse-patient communication. *Collegian*, 24(1), 63-69.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colegn.2015.09.001>
- Crawford, T., Roger, P., & Candlin, S. (2018). The consequences of diverse empathic responses in nurse-patient interactions: A discourse analysis. *Journal of Communication in Healthcare*, 11(2), 87-94. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17538068.2018.1453435>
- den Hertog, R., & Niessen, T. (2021). Taking into account patient preferences in personalised care: Blending types of nursing knowledge in evidence-based practice. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 30(13-14), 1904-1915. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.15743>
- Düdener, E., & Hallaç, S. (2023). The effect of the training of presence in care (TpinCare) on the care-oriented patient-nurse interaction and the caring behaviors of nurses working with oncology patients: A randomized controlled trial. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 68, 103566–103566. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2023.103566>
- El-Shami, E. E. (2023). ‘Commit to sit’ to increase patient satisfaction. *Nursing* 53(9), 53-55.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.NURSE.0000946852.76566.73>
- George, S., Rahmatinick, S., & Ramos, J. (2018). Commit to sit to improve nurse communication. *Critical Care Nurse*, 38(2), 83-85. <https://doi.org/10.4037/ccn2018846>
- Gillespie, D. J., & Schiffman, R. (2018). A critique of the Shannon-Weaver theory of communication and its implications for nursing. *Research and Theory for Nursing Practice*, 32(2), 216-225. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1891/1541-6577.32.2.216>
- Granados-Gámez, G., Sáez-Ruiz, I. M., Márquez-Hernández, V. V., Ybarra-Sagarduy, J. L., Aguilera-Manrique, G., & Gutiérrez-Puertas, L. (2021). Systematic review of measurement properties of self-reported instruments for evaluating therapeutic

communication. *Western Journal of Nursing Research*, 43(8), 791-804.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0193945920970154>

Gunawan, J., Aunguroch, Y., Watson, J., & Marzilli, C. (2022). Nursing administration:

Watson's theory of human caring. *Nursing Science Quarterly*, 35(2), 235–243.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/08943184211070582>

Gutiérrez-Puertas, L., Márquez-Hernández, V. V., Gutiérrez-Puertas, V., Granados-Gámez, G.,

& Aguilera-Manrique, G. (2020). Educational interventions for nursing students to

develop communication skills with patients: A systematic review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(7), 2241.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17072241>

Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and System. (2024, April 24). A note

about HCAHPS “boxes”. <https://www.hcahpsonline.org/en/summary-analyses/>

Hermann, R. M., Long, E., & Trotta, R. L. (2019). Improving patients’ experiences

communicating with nurses and providers in the emergency department. *Journal of*

Emergency Nursing, 45(5), 523-530. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jen.2018.12.001>

Holopainen, G., Nyström, L., & Kasén, A. (2019). The caring encounter in nursing. *Nursing*

Ethics, 26(1), 7-16. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0969733016687161>

Huron (2023). *AIDET patient education*. <https://www.studergroup.com/aidet>

Institute of Healthcare Improvement (2023). *Overview: Person-and family-centered care*.

<https://www.ihl.org/Topics/PFCC/Pages/Overview.aspx>

Institute of Medicine (U.S.) Committee on Quality of Health Care in America. (2001). *Crossing*

the quality chasm: A new health system for the 21st century. Washington (DC): National

Academies Press (US). Available from:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK222265/>

Iowa Model Collaborative. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(3), 175-182.

<https://doi.org:10.1111/wvn.12223>

Irwin, A. J. (2020). Improving patient satisfaction at a rural urgent care center. *Nursing Management*, 49(3), 18-20.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.NURSE.0000552700.35255.a1>

Joint Commission International. (2018). *Communicating clearly and effectively to patients: How to overcome common communication challenges in health care*.

<https://www.jointcommissioninternational.org/>

Katz, A. (2019). Compassion in practice: Difficult conversations in oncology nursing. *Canadian Oncology Nursing Journal*, 29(4), 255.

Krueger, A., Erdman, K., Lemke, J., & Kabir, C. (2021). Examining agreement between nurse and patient perceptions of nursing care attributes in the surgical setting. *Nursing Management*, 52(12), 14-21. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.NUMA.0000800332.41930.ff>

Lam, W., Wong, F. Y., & Chan, A. E. (2020). Factors affecting the levels of satisfaction with nurse-patient communication among oncology patients. *Cancer Nursing*, 43(4), E186-E196. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NCC.0000000000000672>

Li, L., Li, Y., Yin, T., Chen, J., & Shi, F. (2022). A cohort study of the effects of Integrated medical and nursing rounds combined with AIDET communication mode on recovery and quality of life in patients undergoing percutaneous coronary intervention.

Computational and Mathematical Methods in Medicine, 2022

<https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/9489203>

Lidgett, C. D. (2016). Improving the patient experience through a commit to sit service excellence initiative. *Patient Experience Journal* 3(2): 67-72.

<https://doi.org/10.35680/2372-0247.1148>

Lotfi M., Zamanzadeh V., Valizadeh L., Khajehgoodari M. (2019). Assessment of nurse-patient communication and patient satisfaction from nursing care. *Nursing Open* 6(3):1189-1196.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/nop2.316>

Lundberg, K., Jong, M., Jong, M. C., & Porskrog Kristiansen, L. (2020). Patients' experiences of the caring encounter in health promotion practice: a qualitative study in Swedish primary health care. *BMC Family Practice*, 21(1), 1-10. [https://doi.org/10.1186/s12875-020-](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12875-020-01296-6)

[01296-6](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12875-020-01296-6)

McClendon, P. (2017). Authentic caring: Rediscover the essence of nursing. *Nursing*

Management, 48(10), 36-41. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.NUMA.0000524813.18664.7c>

Moore, P. M., Rivera, S., Bravo-Soto, G. A., Olivares, C., & Lawrie, T. A. (2018).

Communication skills training for healthcare professionals working with people who have cancer. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, (7).

<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD003751.pub4>

Naik, A. D. (2022). Measuring patient-centered care to improve hospital experiences of older adults. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 70(12), 3348-3351.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/jgs.18048>

- National Comprehensive Cancer Network. (2023). *Guiding principles for promoting high quality cancer care*. Available from <https://www.nccn.org/business-policy/business/employer-resources/employer-toolkit>
- Pajnkihar, M., McKenna, H. P., Štiglic, G., & Vrbnjak, D. (2017). Fit for practice: Analysis and evaluation of Watson's theory of human caring. *Nursing Science Quarterly*, 30(3), 243–252. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894318417708409>
- Pittsenbargar, J., Amos, G., & Gaudet, J. A. (2015). Commit to sit in radiology. *Radiology Management*, 37(2), 49-51.
- Pratt, H., Moroney, T., & Middleton, R. (2021). The influence of engaging authentically on nurse-patient relationships: A scoping review. *Nursing Inquiry*, 28(2), e12388. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nin.12388>
- Press Ganey Associates, LLC. (2023). *Patient experience*. <https://www.pressganey.com/>
- Register, S. J., Blanchard, E., Belle, A., Viles, A., Moore, S. P., MacLennan, P., & White, M. L. (2020). Using AIDET® education simulations to improve patient experience scores. *Clinical Simulation in Nursing*, 38, 14-17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecns.2019.09.005>
- Rivai, F., Rezeki, S. F., Pasinringi, S. A., & Mangilep, A. U. (2020). Overview of interpersonal communication between nurses and patients in inpatient installation at RSUD HA Sulthan Daeng Radja. *Enfermería Clínica*, 30(56), 134-137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enfcli.2020.06.031>
- Saad, L. (2023, January 13). American sour on US healthcare quality. *Gallup* <https://news.gallup.com/poll/468176/americans-sour-healthcare-quality.aspx>

- Sethi, D., & Rani, M. K. (2017). Communication barrier in health care setting as perceived by nurses and patient. *International Journal of Nursing Education*, 9(4), 30.
<https://doi.org/10.5958/0974-9357.2017.00092.7>
- Sherwood, G., & Barnsteiner, J. (Eds.). (2022). *Quality and safety in nursing: A competency approach to improving outcomes*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Skaggs, M. K. D., Daniels, J. F., Hodge, A. J., & DeCamp, V. L. (2018). Using the evidence-based practice service nursing bundle to increase patient satisfaction. *Journal of Emergency Nursing*, 44(1), 37-45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jen.2017.10.011>
- Speroni, K. G., McLaughlin, M. K., & Friesen, M. A. (2020). Use of evidence-based practice models and research findings in magnet-designated hospitals across the United States: national survey results. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 17(2), 98–107.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12428>
- Takman C. A. S. & Severinsson E. (1999). A description of health care professionals' experiences of encounters with patients in clinical settings. *Journal Advanced Nursing*, 30(6): 1368–1374. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2648.1999.01235.x>
- Taylor, C., Lynn, P., & Bartlett, J. (2023). *Fundamentals of nursing: The art and science of person-centered care* (10th ed.). Wolters Kluwer
- Titler, M. G., Kleiber, C., Steelman, V. J., Rakel, B. A., Budreau, G., Everett, L. Q., Buckwalter, K. C., Tripp-Reimer, T., & Goode, C. J. (2001). The Iowa model of evidence-based practice to promote quality care. *Critical Care Nursing Clinics of North America*, 13(4), 497–509
- Tucker, S., McNett, M., Mazurek Melnyk, B., Hanrahan, K., Hunter, S. C., Kim, B., Cullen, L., & Kitson, A. (2021). Implementation science: Application of evidence-based practice

- models to improve healthcare quality. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 18(2), 76–84. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12495>
- Trotta, R. L., Rao, A. D., McHugh, M. D., Yoho, M., & Cunningham, R. S. (2020). Moving beyond the measure: Understanding patients' experiences of communication with nurses. *Research in Nursing & Health*, 43(6), 568-578. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nur.22087>
- Vega, H., & Hayes, K. (2019). Blending the art and science of nursing. *Nursing2019*, 49(9), 62-63. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.NURSE.0000577752.54139.4e>
- Watson's Caring Science Institute. (2024, April 19). *Caring science measurement tools & research*. <https://www.watsoncaringscience.org/jean-bio/caring-science-theory/research/watson-caritas-patient-score/>

Appendix A

The Iowa Model

Note. Used/reprinted with permission from the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics, copyright 2015.

Appendix B

Articles Searched from CINAHL/EBSCO

Database: CINAHL/EBSCO

Terms	Limitations	# of Articles Retrieved	# of Articles Excluded	# of Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
(communication skills training OR communication methods) AND nurse-patient relations AND empathy	Peer Reviewed, Nursing and Health Professions Published: 2017 to 2023	29	20	9	0
(communication AND empathy AND (nurse-patient relations)) AND (framework or model or theory or approach)	Peer Reviewed, Nursing and Health Professions Published: 2017 to 2023	145	128	17	12
(communication AND (empathy OR emotional intelligence) AND (nurse-patient relations)) AND (framework or model or theory)	Peer Reviewed, Nursing and Health Professions Published: 2017 to 2023	46	33	13	0
(Patient experience or patient satisfaction) AND communication AND nursing	Peer Reviewed, Nursing and Health Professions Published: 2017 to 2023	143	140	3	3
Nurse patient communication AND patient satisfaction	Peer Reviewed, Nursing and Health Professions Published: 2017 to 2023	109	83	26	11

(aidet or aidet communication tool) AND patient satisfaction	Peer Reviewed, Nursing and Health Professions Published: 2017 to 2023	20	13	7	7
commit to sit to improve nurse communication OR commit to sit	Peer Reviewed, Nursing and Health Professions Published: 2016 to 2023	6	1	5	3

Appendix C

Literature Review Table of Evidence

Database: PubMed

Search Terms	Search Options	# of Articles Retrieved	# of Articles Excluded	# of Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
("Nursing"[Mesh] AND "Empathy"[Mesh] AND "Communication"[Mesh])	Peer reviewed, 2017-2022), English	32	29	3	1
("Nursing"[Mesh] AND "Empathy"[Mesh] AND "Communication"[Mesh] AND framework)	Peer reviewed, 2017-2022), English	2	1	1	0

Appendix D

Literature Review Table of Evidence

Database: Cochrane

Search Terms	Search Options	# of Articles Retrieved	# of Articles Excluded	# of Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Nurse Patient Relations	Peer reviewed, Cochrane (2017-2022), English	1	1	0	0
AIDET	Peer reviewed, Cochrane, (2017-2022), English	2	2	0	0
Nurse Communication Framework	Peer reviewed, Cochrane, (2017-2022), English	4	4	0	0
Nursing and Empathy	Peer reviewed, Cochrane, (2017-2022), English	2	2	0	0
Nursing Communication Skills	Peer reviewed, Cochrane, (2017-2022), English	38	36	2	1

Appendix E

Permission to Use Iowa Model

Permission to Use The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

Kimberly Jordan - University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics <survey-bounce@survey.uiowa.edu>
To: Carolina Uranga

Sun 3/5/2023 10:09 AM

You forwarded this message on 3/5/2023 10:14 AM.
If there are problems with how this message is displayed, click here to view it in a web browser.

[External] This email came from an external source.
Do not open attachments or click on links from unknown senders or unexpected emails.

You have permission, as requested today, to review and/or reproduce *The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care*. Click the link below to open.

[Iowa Model - 2015.pdf](#)

Copyright is retained by University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics. **Permission is not granted for placing on the internet.**

Reference: Iowa Model Collaborative. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(3), 175-182. doi:10.1111/wvn.12223

In written material, please add the following statement:

Used/reprinted with permission from the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics, copyright 2015. For permission to use or reproduce, please contact the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics at 319-384-9098.

Note. Email permission to use the Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care (Revised 2015). Copyright is retained by the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics.

Appendix F

Institutional Review Board Approval Initial – California State University

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON

Office of Research and Sponsored Projects

P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7719 / F 657-278-7238

APPROVAL NOTICE

*From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton*

August 24, 2023

**From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board**

To: Pt: Carolina Uranga

Application No. HSR-23-24-33

Study Title: Enhancing the Nurse-Patient Relationship and Patient Satisfaction

Re: Initial Exempt Review

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be Category 2.(i). Research that only includes interactions involving educational tests (cognitive, diagnostic, aptitude, achievement), survey procedures, interview procedures, or observation of public behavior (including visual or auditory recording) if at least one of the following criteria is met:

The information obtained is recorded by the investigator in such a manner that the identity of the human subjects cannot readily be ascertained, directly or through identifiers linked to the subjects;

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

In addition, all research personnel must follow the institutional safety guidelines outlined for CSUF's Presidential Directive 22. Additional information can be found in the [TITANS RETURN: COVID-19 Recovery](#) website.

Appendix F

Institutional Review Board Approval Initial – California State University

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participants and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Since your proposal was determined to be exempt, there is no further review or annual renewal required by the CSUF IRB. **However, any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires re-submission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation.** Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-reference title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any changes in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chair of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that their responsibility for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

The institution has an Assurance on file with the Office of Human Research Protections. The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Cc: IRB Office
Sadeeka Al-Majid

ADDITIONAL RESOURCES:

Withdrawal - A withdrawal submission notifies the Research Compliance Office that you no longer wish to submit your initial submission and want to withdraw the study. Withdrawn studies are marked as finalized and can no longer be modified. You may create a withdrawal submission at any point once an initial submission has been created, until it has been approved. If the initial submission had been approved, you must create a closure submission in order to close the study if you no longer wish to conduct the research. For additional guidance, access the step-by-step instructions for [Cayuse IRB: Submitting a Withdrawal Notification](#).

Modification - If you wish to change any of the details of the study after it has been approved, you must submit a modification which must be approved before you can proceed with the changes. Modifications will only be available after initial approval is issued. Modifications will be linked with the initial application and you will make revisions to the initial application based on the modifications you are requesting. For additional guidance, access the step-by-step instructions for [Cayuse IRB: Submitting a Modification](#).

Renewal - When a study is nearing its expiration date, you must submit a renewal request in order to continue with the research. Expiration notices will be emailed from Cayuse. Renewals, like modifications, will only be available after initial approval is issued. For additional guidance, access the step-by-step instructions for [Cayuse IRB: Submitting a Renewal](#).

Incident - You must submit an incident report to inform the IRB Office of any adverse incidents, as required by your

Appendix F

Institutional Review Board Approval Initial– California State University

institution. Incident reports may be submitted at any time after a study has been approved, including after it has been closed. More than one incident report may be created for a given study, as needed. For additional guidance, access the step-by-step instructions for [Cayuse IRB: Submitting an Incident Report](#).

Closure - A closure submission indicates that the research is complete and will not be continuing. Closed studies are marked as finalized and can no longer be modified. For additional guidance, access the step-by-step instructions for [Cayuse IRB: Submitting a Closure Request](#).

Appendix G

Institutional Review Board Approval Amendment – California State University

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON

Office of Research and Sponsored Projects

P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7719 / F 657-278-7238

APPROVAL NOTICE - Amendment

*From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton*

August 29, 2023

**From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board**

To: Pt: Carolina Uranga

Application No. HSR-23-24-33

Study Title: Enhancing the Nurse-Patient Relationship and Patient Satisfaction

Re: Modification Exempt Approval

The request for protocol change you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed and approved. Your proposal is determined to be Category 2.(i). Research that only includes interactions involving educational tests (cognitive, diagnostic, aptitude, achievement), survey procedures, interview procedures, or observation of public behavior (including visual or auditory recording) if at least one of the following criteria is met:

The information obtained is recorded by the investigator in such a manner that the identity of the human subjects cannot readily be ascertained, directly or through identifiers linked to the subjects;

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any department or additional approvals which may be required.

In addition, all research personnel must follow the institutional safety guidelines outlined for CSUF's Presidential Directive 22. Additional information can be found in the [TITANS RETURN: COVID-19 Recovery website](#).

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participants and that you follow the

Appendix G

Institutional Review Board Approval Amendment – California State University

plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Since your proposal was determined to be exempt, there is no further review or annual renewal required by the CSUF IRB. **However, any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires re-submission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation.** Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-referenced title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any change in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chairman of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that s/he is responsible for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

This institution has an Assurance on file with the Office for Human Research Protections. The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Cc: IRB Office
Sadeeka Al-Majid

ADDITIONAL RESOURCES:

Withdrawal - A withdrawal submission notifies the Research Compliance Office that you no longer wish to submit your initial submission and want to withdraw the study. Withdrawn studies are marked as finalized and can no longer be modified. You may create a withdrawal submission at any point once an initial submission has been created, until it has been approved. If the initial submission had been approved, you must create a closure submission in order to close the study if you no longer wish to conduct the research. For additional guidance, access the step-by-step instructions for [Cayuse IRB: Submitting a Withdrawal Notification](#).

Modification - If you wish to change any of the details of the study after it has been approved, you must submit a modification which must be approved before you can proceed with the changes. Modifications will only be available after initial approval is issued. Modifications will be linked with the initial application and you will make revisions to the initial application based on the modifications you are requesting. For additional guidance, access the step-by-step instructions for [Cayuse IRB: Submitting a Modification](#).

Renewal - When a study is nearing its expiration date, you must submit a renewal request in order to continue with the research. Expiration notices will be emailed from Cayuse. Renewals, like modifications, will only be available after initial approval is issued. For additional guidance, access the step-by-step instructions for [Cayuse IRB: Submitting a Renewal](#).

Incident - You must submit an incident report to inform the IRB Office of any adverse incidents, as required by your institution. Incident reports may be submitted at any time after a study has been approved, including after it has been closed. More than one incident report may be created for a given study, as needed. For additional guidance,

Appendix G

Institutional Review Board Approval Amendment – California State University

access the step-by-step instructions for [Cayuse IRB: Submitting an Incident Report](#).

Closure - A closure submission indicates that the research is complete and will not be continuing. Closed studies are marked as finalized and can no longer be modified. For additional guidance, access the step-by-step instructions for [Cayuse IRB: Submitting a Closure Request](#).

Appendix H

Institutional Review Board Approval Initial – City of Hope

Clinical Research Protections
1500 East Duarte Road
Duarte, CA 91010-3000
Phone: (626) 218-2700
IRBeSubmit@coh.org

Institutional Review Board Notification of Determination of Exemption

Date: August 11, 2023

To: Carolina Uranga, MSN, AGCNS-BC, OCN, NPD-BC, Principal Investigator
City of Hope - Quality Risk & Regulatory Mgmt

From: Rubi Linares-Orozco, Director
Clinical Research Protections

COH Protocol #/Ref #: 23537 / 251520

Protocol Title: Enhancing the Nurse-Patient Relationship and Patient Satisfaction

Regulatory Sponsor: CITY OF HOPE (COH)

Action Date: 08/11/2023

Action: EXEMPT

The information provided for the above submission was evaluated and determined to meet the criteria for exemption from IRB review under 45CFR46.104 (d). When the research is completed, please submit a "Study Closure" submission. The Principal Investigator assumes the responsibilities for the protection of human subjects as outlined in the COH HRPP SOP Policy.

Exempt Category3: Research involving benign behavioral interventions in conjunction with the collection of information from an adult subject through verbal or written responses (including data entry) or audiovisual recording if the subject prospectively agrees to the intervention and information collection and at least one of the following criteria is met: (B.) Any disclosure of the human subjects' responses outside the research would not reasonably place the subjects at risk of criminal or civil liability or be damaging to the subjects' financial standing, employability, educational advancement, or reputation.

Please note that if any changes occur for this research, or any issues arise that may increase the risk of participants, or any complaints are received, notification to the IRB is required.

The following documents were reviewed:

- Information Sheet(s): 23537_Consent_Info_Sheet_(English)_8.11.23
- Data Collection Form(s): 23537_DPF_Non-Identifier_08.11.23
- Other: 23537_MAT_Letter_08.11.23
23537_MAT_Email_08.11.23
23537_MAT_EmailReminder_08.11.23

Please note the following:

1. It is understood that the activities described for this research study are being done in support of a

Appendix H

Institutional Review Board Approval Initial – City of Hope

Doctoral Nurse Practitioner (DNP) program at the California State University Fullerton. Any resulting data will be deidentified.

If you have questions or concerns about this submission, please contact Rubi Linares-Orozco or IRBeSubmit@coh.org.

Appendix I

Institutional Review Board Approval – City of Hope

Clinical Research Protections
1500 East Duarte Road
Duarte, CA 91010-3000
Phone: (626) 218-2700
IRBeSubmit@coh.org

Institutional Review Board Notification of Determination of Exemption

Date: August 28, 2023

To: Carolina Uranga, MSN, AGCNS-BC, OCN, NPD-BC, Principal Investigator
City of Hope - Quality Risk & Regulatory Mgmt

From: Rubi Linares-Orozco, Director
Clinical Research Protections

COH Protocol #/Ref #: 23537 / 253451

Protocol Title: Enhancing the Nurse-Patient Relationship and Patient Satisfaction

Regulatory Sponsor: CITY OF HOPE (COH)

Action Date: 08/28/2023

Action: EXEMPT

The information provided for the above submission was evaluated and determined to meet the criteria for exemption from IRB review under 45CFR46.104 (d). When the research is completed, please submit a "Study Closure" submission. The Principal Investigator assumes the responsibilities for the protection of human subjects as outlined in the COH HRPP SOP Policy.

Research involving benign behavioral interventions in conjunction with the collection of information from an adult subject through verbal or written responses (including data entry) or audiovisual recording if the subject prospectively agrees to the intervention and information collection and at least one of the following criteria is met: (ii.) Any disclosure of the human subjects' responses outside the research would not reasonably place the subjects at risk of criminal or civil liability or be damaging to the subjects' financial standing, employability, educational advancement, or reputation. (Exempt Category 3)

Please note that if any changes occur for this research, or any issues arise that may increase the risk of participants, or any complaints are received, notification to the IRB is required.

The following documents were reviewed:

- Information Sheet(s): 23537_Consent_Info_Sheet_(English)_8.28.23
- Other: 23537_MAT_EmailReminder_08.25.23
23537_MAT_Letter_08.25.23

If you have questions or concerns about this submission, please contact Joyanna Ko or IRBeSubmit@coh.org.

Appendix J

Institutional Approval Letter to Use the Project Site

1500 East Duarte Road,
SEA #0103
Duarte, CA 91010-3000
Phone 626-218-2688
www.cityofhope.org

California State University, Fullerton
Doctor of Nursing Practice Program
800 N. State College Blvd.
Fullerton, CA 92831-3599

May 22, 2023

To Whom It May Concern:

This letter is to show that, I, LaNice Berry, as the Executive Director of Solid Tumor Nursing at City of Hope National Medical Center, give Carolina Uranga as the project lead permission to conduct the project titled: *Enhancing Nurse-Patient Interactions and Patient Satisfaction* on East Hospital B (formerly EHA).

Upon obtaining all necessary clearances from the Professional Governance Steering Committee at City of Hope National Medical Center, and after obtaining the necessary IRB determination/ approval, the above-named project lead is allowed to:

1. Collect pre-and-post knowledge survey data from EHB registered nursing staff including nursing demographic data at baseline (years of experience, shift, and nursing degree).
2. Access necessary data: EHB pre-and-post HCAHPS survey results of Domain: Communication with Nurses.
3. Conduct necessary interactions with staff/patients relevant to their project. Including in person PowerPoint presentation and training on The HOPE Experience Program and Commit to Sit communication strategies. Random weekly observation audits of nurses to assess the use of both communication strategies during their shift.
4. Distribute via staff email and on the unit: pre-and post-knowledge survey, project flyer, PowerPoint education presentation, and knowledge survey via QR code.

The project lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are following the policies that govern practice, HIPPA, and research and research-related regulations at City of Hope National Medical Center and its covered entities.

If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me at 626.218.2688.

LaNice Berry

LaNice Berry, MSN, RN, NEA-BC
Executive Director Nursing, Solid Tumor

Appendix K

Permission to use The HOPE Experience Educational Material

RE: The HOPE Experience: Team Training Material

Reg Randles
To: Carolina Uranga
Cc: Dung Banh; Adineh Poulatian

Reply
 Reply All
 Forward

Fri 7/7/2023 12:00 PM

You replied to this message on 7/11/2023 3:33 PM.

The HOPE Experience Observation & Feedback Tool.pdf
187 KB

The HOPE Experience Team Implementation for Carolina Uranga.pptx
2 MB

Hello, Carolina~

I hope this email finds you well. Attached, please find The HOPE Experience Observation and Feedback tool and a copy of The HOPE Experience Team Implementation for you to reference and reconstruct as necessary. We'd love to see the final model of your audit tool and PowerPoint presentation. 😊

After your submission to and approval by the Institutional Review Board, please share your anticipated start/complete dates and any other milestones you'd like to socialize with us.

Best of fortune Carolina, and thank you for your commitment to reinforcing the practice of The HOPE Experience and introducing the Commit to Sit framework!

Kind regards,

Reg

Reginald A. Randles, MOL, SHRM-CP
Senior Manager | Patient Experience

rrandles@coh.org
Phone 626-803-3204

Follow City of Hope:
[Facebook](#) | [Twitter](#) | [Instagram](#) | [LinkedIn](#) | [YouTube](#) | [Blog](#)

From: Carolina Uranga <CUranga@coh.org>

Appendix L

Knowledge Survey Questions

QUESTIONS	CORRECT ANSWERS
<p>The HOPE Experience training program core principles include all of the following EXCEPT:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connect with Heart • Offer service with collaboration* and a sense of urgency • Provide care plans • End with excellence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide care plans
<p>The HOPE Experience can improve patient satisfaction scores.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • True • False 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • True
<p>Commit to sit is a communication strategy that can improve patient satisfaction.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • True • False 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • True
<p>The nurse-patient relationship includes the following humanistic factors. Check all that apply)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compassion • Sympathy • Therapeutic touch • Active listening 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compassion • Therapeutic touch • Active listening
<p>Effective communication can...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increases patient anxiety • Increases length of stay • Increases the patient's sense of control and confidence • Decreases patient satisfaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increases the patient's sense of control and confidence

Appendix M

DNP Project Timeline

DNP Project Timeline

Enhancing the Nurse-Patient Communication and Patient Satisfaction

March – April 2023	May – June 2023	July – September 2023	October – December 2023	January – March 2024	April – May 2024
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete Review of Literature • Identify Communication strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project site identified • Obtain a Letter of Approval from Project Site Sponsor • Present and defend project to Team Lead and Member • Receive approval from Team Leader and Member 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply for IRB with CSUF and Project Site • Obtain IRB approval from both sites • Obtain approval from appropriate committee to proceed with project implementation • Start data collection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finalize data collection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyze results • Create poster • Submit abstract for poster presentation at CSUF HHD Research Showcase 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present Poster at CSUF HHD Research Showcase • Defend and Present Project to Project Lead and Member

Appendix N

Nurse-Patient Interactions Self-Assessment

4/29/24, 8:05 PM

DNP Project: Consent & Baseline Nursing Questionnaire

Nurse - Patient Interactions: Self-Assessment

Please consider your patient interactions on a day-to-day basis and answer the following self-assessment questions. There is no right or wrong answers. Goal is to assess your effectiveness of the educational intervention.

17

H1-During patient interactions I explain processes/procedures and write processes/procedures on the whiteboard *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

18

H2-I call patient by their preferred name. *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

19

H3-When entering the room I makes eye contact with patient? *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

Appendix N-Continued

Nurse Patient Interactions Self-Assessment

4/29/24, 8:05 PM

DNP Project: Consent & Baseline Nursing Questionnaire

20

H4-I introduces myself to patient? *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

21

H5-I acknowledge everyone in the room? (Ex: makes eye contact) *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

22

H6-I introduces my role? (Ex: I state I am their nurse for the shift) *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

23

H7-I sit during patient encounters? *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

Appendix N-Continued

Nurse-Patient Interactions Self-Assessment

4/29/24, 8:05 PM

DNP Project: Consent & Baseline Nursing Questionnaire

24

O1-I explain what I am going to do - processes/procedures. (Ex Write processes/procedures on whiteboard) *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

25

O2-I ask if patient/family has any questions? *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

26

O3-I respond to the patient/family's questions? *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

27

O4-I take ownership of concerns until resolved if applicable. *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

Appendix N (Continued)

Nurse-Patient Interactions Self-Assessment

4/29/24, 8:05 PM

DNP Project: Consent & Baseline Nursing Questionnaire

28

P1-I listen to patient/family and validate by verbal and non-verbal cues. (Ex: Nod my head or asks questions to clarify and understand issue) *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

29

P2-I empathize with Compassion. (Ex: Use therapeutic touch by touching patient's arm or shoulder, holding hand using hand over hand technique; or show concern about pain/suffering) *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

30

P3-I respect cultural uniqueness by demonstrating cultural humility. (Ex: Ask patient what they prefer to be called; leave door open or closed, food preferences; patient's personal items - pictures or drawings; or preferred language, personal space preference) *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

Appendix N (Continued)

Nurse-Patient Interactions Self-Assessment

4/29/24, 8:05 PM

DNP Project: Consent & Baseline Nursing Questionnaire

31

P4-I explain next steps of processes and procedures. (Ex: Verbally explain and/or update whiteboard with upcoming tests/procedures) *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

32

E1-I share contact information with patient/family. (Ex: Update whiteboard with RN Name) *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

33

E2-I asks if there is anything else I can do before leaving the room? *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

34

E3-I sincerely thank patient and exit with respect. *

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

Appendix O

Consent to Participate

Principal Investigator: Carolina Uranga
 Department/Division: Quality, Risk & Regulatory Management
 Telephone number: 626.218.3460

INFORMATION SHEET FOR PARTICIPATION IN RESEARCH ACTIVITIES

Enhancing the Nurse-Patient Relationship and Patient Satisfaction
 COH Protocol: #23537

KEY INFORMATION

You are invited to participate in a research study. The purpose of this research study is to examine the nurses' demographics, knowledge of the nurse-patient relationship, and self-assessment of patient interaction of nurses who care for Medical Oncology patients on East Hospital B. The information and knowledge gained from your participation in this research study may benefit patients you provide care to and others in the future.

Participants in this study will 1) complete a baseline survey with questions regarding nurses' demographics, knowledge, and self-assessment of patient interactions, 2) participate in a 10-minute educational in-service on The HOPE Experience and Communication Strategies during work hours on the weekend and during staff meeting, 3) complete a post knowledge survey after educational in-service, 4) complete a follow-up survey approximately two months post educational in-service, 5) be observed in patient interactions pre-and post-education. Further details are included below.

There are no major risks associated with this research study.

You do not have to join this research study. If you are interested in learning more about this study, please continue to read below.

- I. **PURPOSE OF THIS RESEARCH STUDY:** You have been invited to participate in a research study. The purpose of this study is to examine the nurses' demographics, knowledge of the nurse-patient relationship, and self-assessment of patient interaction of nurses who care for Medical Oncology patients on East Hospital B. You have been chosen for this study because you meet the following qualifications: The information and knowledge gained from your participation in this research study may benefit patients you provide care to and others in the future.

INFORMED CONSENT INFORMATION SHEET

Appendix O (Continued)

Consent to Participate

Page 2 of 4

If you agree to take part in this study, you will be asked to complete a baseline online or paper survey/questionnaire (7 minutes) and it will ask about your demographics, knowledge questions, and self-assessment of patient interactions. Weekly reminders to complete the baseline online or paper survey/questionnaire will be provided. Immediately post the educational intervention you will complete an online or paper knowledge survey/questionnaire (2 minutes). One month post intervention you will be asked to complete an online or paper survey/questionnaire and it will ask you the same baseline knowledge and self-assessment of patient interactions questions (7 minutes). Weekly reminders will be provided to complete the post intervention online or paper survey/questionnaire. You will also be asked to participate in pre-and post-observations of your patient interactions. The observation audits will include the frequency of nurses utilizing The HOPE Experience communication and Commit to Sit strategies. For these audits the PI will be observing your patient interactions. We are inviting all the EHB registered nurses to participate in this research study. Data will be collected, and results will be aggregated for reporting purposes. The information will be disseminated internally (City of Hope-EHB, The HOPE Experience Department) and externally (California State University, Fullerton, Oncology Nursing Society). The surveys are not validated and are investigational.

- II. **BACKGROUND:** Nurses are involved in direct patient care 24 hours a day and a patient's hospital experience relies upon the nurses they encounter during their hospital stay. The nurse-patient relationship can be enhanced by nurses skilled in communication along with the patient's understanding of healthcare quality and treatment outcomes. Effective nursing communication can benefit nurses by improving their self-efficacy, confidence, and strengthen patient-centered care.
- III. **WHAT WILL BE DONE:** You will be provided with an email link or paper surveys/questionnaires to complete. The baseline survey consists of 35 questions aimed at characterizing nurse demographics, knowledge questions regarding the nurse-patient relationship and The HOPE Experience, and self-assessment of patient interactions based on The HOPE Experience practices. We estimate that it will take about 7 minutes to complete. The education is estimated to take 10 minutes and will consist of a PowerPoint presentation of The HOPE Experience program, nurse patient relationship and Commit to Sit communication strategy. The HOPE Experience program is City of Hope's commitment to exceptional and individualized care experiences for all patients, caregivers, and each other. It symbolizes our values and actions to provide the best medical care and understanding that a patient's cancer journey is more than their diagnosis and treatment. Following the educational in-service participants will complete a knowledge survey.

INFORMED CONSENT INFORMATION SHEET

Appendix O (Continued)

Consent to Participate

Page 3 of 4

An online or paper survey will be provided via email or available via QR code.

- IV. **POSSIBLE BENEFITS:** The information and knowledge gained from your participation in this research study may improve your nursing knowledge and benefit patients you provide care to in the future.
- V. **RISKS:** The risks and discomforts of this study are a possible breach of confidentiality and possibly becoming tired from the amount of time needed to complete the surveys.
- VI. **ALTERNATIVES TO PARTICIPATION:** Your alternative is to choose not to participate in this study. Your participation in this research study is voluntary, and you can opt out of the survey at any point. Choosing not to participate will not interfere with any future treatment at or any relationship with City of Hope.
- VII. **CONFIDENTIALITY OF INFORMATION:**
- Data collected will be anonymous and results will be aggregated for reporting purposes. The information will be disseminated internally (City of Hope-EHB, The HOPE Experience Department) and externally (California State University-Fullerton, Oncology Nursing Society). Any data collected will be used solely for the purpose of the project unless plans for future research are described below
- By participating in the survey, you also allow the researchers to make your information available (as needed) to City of Hope Institutional Review Board (IRB) Office, the Office for Human Research Protections (OHRP), the National Cancer Institute (NCI), and other regulatory agencies as required by law. If information learned from this project is published, no identifiable information will be shared as the survey does not collect any personal information.
- Future Use of Research Information**
- The information that has been collected for this research study will not be used for future research studies or shared with other researchers beyond the research activities described in this consent form.
- VIII. **OFFER TO ANSWER QUESTIONS AND IMPARTIAL THIRD PARTY:** If you have any further questions, you can contact Carolina Uranga at curanga@coh.org or on extension 83460.
- IX. **VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION WITH RIGHT OF REFUSAL:** You have been informed that your participation in this research study is voluntary. You are free to withdraw your consent for participation in this project without any loss of benefits, penalty, or interference with any relationship with City of Hope.

INFORMED CONSENT INFORMATION SHEET

Appendix O (Continued)

Consent to Participate

Page 4 of 4

- X. **IRB REVIEW AND IMPARTIAL THIRD PARTY:** This research study has been reviewed and approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB). A representative of that Board, from the Office of Human Research Subjects Protection, is available to discuss the review process or your rights as a research subject. The telephone number of the Office of Human Research Subjects Protection is (626) 256-HOPE (4673) ext. 62700.

CONFIRMATION OF CONSENT: By completing and submitting the paper or online survey, you are consenting to have the collected information used as part of this research study.

INFORMED CONSENT INFORMATION SHEET

Appendix P

Observation Tool

Date				
Shift DAY/NIGHT				
Connects with Heart	YES/NO/NA	YES/NO/NA	YES/NO/NA	YES/NO/NA
H1-When entering room makes eye contact with patient				
H2-Introduces themselves to patient				
H3-Acknowledges everyone in the room? (eye contact)				
H4-Introduces their role? (states they are the nurse for the shift)				
H5-Calls patient by name?				
H6-Sits during encounter				
O- Offer service with Collaboration* and a sense of urgency	YES/NO/NA	YES/NO/NA	YES/NO/NA	YES/NO/NA
O1-Explains what they are going to do - processes/procedures. (Writes processes/procedures on whiteboard)				
O2-Ask if patient/ family has questions?				
O3-Responds to patient/ family's questions?				
O4-Takes ownership of concerns until resolved if applicable.				
Personalize	YES/NO/NA	YES/NO/NA	YES/NO/NA	YES/NO/NA
P1-Listens to patient/family and validates by verbal and non-verbal cues. (Nurse nods head or asks questions to clarify and understand issue)				
P2-Empathizes with Compassion. (Therapeutic touch to patient's arm or shoulder, holding hand using hand over hand technique; or concerned about pain/suffering)				
P3-Respects cultural uniqueness by demonstrating cultural humility (Asks preferred name; leave door open or closed, food preferences; patient's personal items - pictures or drawings; preferred language, or personal space preference)				
P4-Explains next steps for processes and procedures? (Verbally explains and/or updates whiteboard with upcoming tests/procedures)				
End with Excellence	YES/NO/NA	YES/NO/NA	YES/NO/NA	YES/NO/NA
E1-Shares contact information with patient/ family? (Updates whiteboard Name)				
E2-Asks if there is anything else he/she can do before leaving the room?				
E3-Sincerely thanks and exits with respect?				

Appendix Q

Demographic Characteristics

Participant Demographics

Variable	n (%)
Shift	
Day	22 (62.86%)
Night	13 (37.14%)
Years of Experience at City of Hope	
Less than 1 year	12 (34.29%)
2-5 years	17 (48.57%)
6-10 years	3 (8.57%)
11-20 years	1 (2.86%)
21 years or greater	2 (5.71%)
Years of Nursing Experience	
Less than 1 year	1 (2.86%)
2-5 years	6 (17.14%)
6-10 years	17 (48.57%)
11-20 years	8 (22.86%)
21 years or greater	3 (8.57%)
Highest Nursing Education Degree	
BSN	31 (88.57%)
MSN	4 (11.43%)
Gender	
Female	29 (82.86%)
Male	5 (14.29%)
Prefer Not to Answer	1 (2.86%)
Ethnicity	
Hispanic/non-Latino	8 (22.86%)
Non-Hispanic/Non-Latino	27 (77.15%)
Race	
Caucasian	3 (8.57%)
White	5 (14.29%)
Asian	25 (71.43%)
Native American	1 (2.86%)
Pacific Islander/Hawaiian	1 (2.86%)
Received The HOPE Experience Training	

Yes	16 (45.71%)
No	7 (20.00%)
Not Sure	12 (34.29%)

Appendix R
Knowledge Survey

Mean, Standard Deviation, and Sample Size for Points by Timepoint

Timepoint	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>n</i>
1 (Baseline)	3.51	0.92	35
2 (Post-intervention)	4.47	0.60	40
3 (One-Month Post Intervention)	3.79	0.54	19

Appendix S

The HOPE Experience Self-Assessment Survey Composite Scores

HOPE Categories Composite Score Subjective - Self-Assessment Survey

The HOPE Experience Program Pre (N=35) & Post (N=19) Categories Composite Score	
H – Connect with Heart	<i>p</i>=.440
O – Offer service with collaboration and a sense of urgency	<i>p</i>=.424
P – Personalize	<i>p</i>=.296
E – End with excellence	<i>p</i>=.821
Pre/Post ALL HOPE Categories Composite <i>p</i>=.479	

Appendix T

The HOPE Experience Paired Observation Composite Scores

HOPE Categories Composite Score Objective - Paired Observations

The HOPE Experience Programs Categories Pre (N=32) & Post (N=32) Categories Composite Score	
H – Connect with Heart	<i>p</i> =.768
O – Offer service with collaboration and a sense of urgency	<i>p</i> =.009
P – Personalize	<i>p</i> =.229
E – End with excellence	<i>p</i> =.021
Pre/Post ALL HOPE Categories Composite <i>p</i>=.001	

Appendix U

Commit to Sit Self-Assessment Survey and Observations

Commit to Sit

• Pre/Post Nursing
(Survey)

The result of the **two-tailed independent samples** t-test was significant based on an alpha value of .05, $t(52) = -3.42, p = .001$

Pre/Post HOPE Experience
(Observations)

The result of the **two-tailed paired samples** t-test was significant based on an alpha value of .05, $t(31) = -3.75, p < .001$

Appendix V

Mean CAHPS Top Box Score Communication with Nursing

